

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

SERENA

Data Management Plan

27/11/2024

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Table of Contents

1	Datasets management and description	13
1.1	SERENA T1.1 – Stakeholder database development.....	13
1.1.1	Objectives and Data Summary	13
1.1.2	FAIR data.....	13
1.1.3	Allocation of resources.....	14
1.1.4	Data security.....	14
1.1.5	Ethical aspects	14
1.1.6	Other.....	15
1.2	SERENA T1.2 – Survey Results – Alignment of Terminology	15
1.2.1	Data summary	15
1.2.2	FAIR data.....	15
1.2.3	Allocation of resources.....	15
1.2.4	Data security.....	15
1.2.5	Ethical aspects	15
1.2.6	Other.....	16
1.2.7	References.....	16
1.3	SERENA T1.4 – Definition of scenarios - Survey results	16
1.3.1	Data summary	16
1.3.2	FAIR data.....	17
1.3.3	Allocation of resources.....	17
1.3.4	Data security.....	17
1.3.5	Ethical aspects	18
1.3.6	Other.....	18
1.4	SERENA T3.1 – Currently available assessments of soil threats and ecosystem services: data, metadata, and methodologies (D3.1.1) and Critical analysis of the experiences at member state level (D3.2v1).....	18
1.4.1	Data summary	18
1.4.2	FAIR data.....	19

1.4.3	Allocation of resources	19
1.4.4	Data security.....	19
1.4.5	Ethical aspects	19
1.4.6	Other.....	19
1.5	SERENA T3.1 – Currently available assessments of soil threats and ecosystem services: data, metadata, and methodologies - update (D3.1.2) and Critical analysis of the experiences at member state level - extension (D3.2v2).....	19
1.5.1	Data summary	20
1.5.2	FAIR data.....	20
1.5.3	Allocation of resources.....	21
1.5.4	Data security.....	21
1.5.5	Ethical aspects	21
1.5.6	Other.....	21
1.6	SERENA T3.2 - Map of Scenarios of Soil Threats and Soil Ecosystem Services in AT	21
1.6.1	Data summary	21
1.6.2	FAIR data.....	22
1.6.3	Allocation of resources.....	22
1.6.4	Data security.....	22
1.6.5	Ethical aspects	23
1.7	SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil sealing of Austria	23
1.7.1	Data summary	23
1.7.2	FAIR data.....	23
1.7.3	Allocation of resources.....	24
1.7.4	Data security.....	24
1.7.5	Ethical aspects	24
1.8	SERENA T3.3 - Literature review	24
1.8.1	Data summary	24
1.8.2	FAIR data.....	25
1.8.3	Allocation of resources.....	25
1.8.4	Data security.....	26
1.8.5	Ethical aspects	26
1.9	SERENA T3.3 - SERENA EJPSOIL France climatic and agricultural change modelling datasets	26
1.9.1	Data summary.....	26
1.9.2	FAIR data.....	26
1.9.3	Allocation of resources	27

1.9.4	Data security	27
1.9.5	Ethical aspects	27
1.9.6	References	27
1.10	SERENA T3.2 - SERENA EJPSOIL cookbook map of soil erosion risk of Flanders (Belgium): SERENA_EJPSOIL_BE_Flanders_EROSION_SOILLOSS_cookbook.....	28
1.10.1	Data summary	28
1.10.2	FAIR data.....	28
1.10.3	Allocation of resources.....	30
1.10.4	Data security.....	30
1.10.5	Ethical aspects	30
1.10.6	Other.....	30
1.11	SERENA T3.2 - SERENA EJPSOIL cookbook map of soil organic carbon of Flanders (Belgium): SERENA_EJPSOIL_BE_Flanders_SOCLOSS_SOC_0-20cm_cookbook	31
1.11.1	Data summary	31
1.11.2	FAIR data.....	31
1.11.3	Allocation of resources.....	33
1.11.4	Data security.....	33
1.11.5	Ethical aspects	33
1.11.6	Other.....	33
1.12	SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil sealing of Flanders (Belgium): SERENA_EJPSOIL_BE_Flanders_SOILSEALING_SEALINGDEGREE.....	34
1.12.1	Data summary	34
1.12.2	FAIR data.....	34
1.12.3	Allocation of resources.....	35
1.12.4	Data security.....	35
1.12.5	Ethical aspects	36
1.13	SERENA T3.2 - Map of SESs/STs Bundles for Czechia (EU)	36
1.13.1	Data summary	36
1.13.2	FAIR data.....	36
1.13.3	Allocation of resources.....	38
1.13.4	Data security.....	38
1.13.5	Ethical aspects	38
1.13.6	References.....	38
1.14	SERENA T3.2 - Map of Net Ecosystem Productivity of Moravia region-Czechia	38
1.14.1	Data summary	38
1.14.2	FAIR data.....	39

1.14.3	Allocation of resources	40
1.14.4	Data security.....	40
1.14.5	Ethical aspects	40
1.14.6	References.....	40
1.15	SERENA T3.2 - Map of compaction projected under climate (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios) and land use change for Czechia.....	41
1.15.1	Data summary	41
1.15.2	FAIR data.....	43
1.15.3	Allocation of resources.....	44
1.15.4	Data security.....	44
1.15.5	Ethical aspects	44
1.15.6	References.....	45
1.16	SERENA T3.2 - Net Ecosystem Productivity of Peipsiääre municipality, Estonia.....	45
1.16.1	Data summary	45
1.16.2	FAIR data.....	45
1.16.3	Allocation of resources.....	46
1.16.4	Data security.....	46
1.16.5	Ethical aspects	47
1.16.6	Other.....	47
1.17	SERENA T3.2 - Impacts of Climate Change Scenarios on Net Ecosystem Productivity in Peipsiääre Municipality, Estonia	47
1.17.1	Data summary	47
1.17.2	FAIR data.....	48
1.17.3	Allocation of resources.....	48
1.17.4	Data security.....	49
1.17.5	Ethical aspects	49
1.17.6	Other.....	49
1.18	SERENA T3.4 - Maps of Soil Organic Carbon Loss Scenarios in Elva Parish, Estonia	49
1.18.1	Data summary	49
1.18.2	FAIR data.....	50
1.18.3	Allocation of resources.....	51
1.18.4	Data security.....	51
1.18.5	Ethical aspects	51
1.18.6	Other.....	51
1.19	SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil organic carbon loss of mineral soils in Estonia	51
1.19.1	Data summary	51

1.19.2	FAIR data.....	52
1.19.3	Allocation of resources.....	53
1.19.4	Data security.....	53
1.19.5	Ethical aspects.....	53
1.20	SERENA T3.2 - Map of SESs/STs Bundles for Estonian agricultural land.....	53
1.20.1	Data summary.....	53
1.20.2	FAIR data.....	53
1.20.3	Allocation of resources.....	54
1.20.4	Data security.....	55
1.20.5	Ethical aspects.....	55
1.21	SERENA T3.2 - Erosion control map of Hungary.....	55
1.21.1	Data summary.....	55
1.21.2	FAIR data.....	55
1.21.3	Allocation of resources.....	56
1.21.4	Data security.....	56
1.21.5	Ethical aspects.....	56
1.22	SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil loss by water erosion of Hungary.....	57
1.22.1	Data summary.....	57
1.22.2	FAIR data.....	57
1.22.3	Allocation of resources.....	58
1.22.4	Data security.....	58
1.22.5	Ethical aspects.....	58
1.23	SERENA T3.2 - Soil organic carbon concentration map for the topsoil of Hungary.....	58
1.23.1	Data summary.....	58
1.23.2	FAIR data.....	59
1.23.3	Allocation of resources.....	60
1.23.4	Data security.....	60
1.23.5	Ethical aspects.....	60
1.24	SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil loss by water erosion of the Ireland.....	60
1.24.1	Data summary.....	60
1.24.2	FAIR data.....	61
1.24.3	Allocation of resources.....	62
1.24.4	Data security.....	62
1.24.5	Ethical aspects.....	62
1.24.6	References.....	62

1.25	SERENA T3.2 - Map of Net Ecosystem Productivity for county level assessment in Ireland	62
1.25.1	Data summary	62
1.25.2	FAIR data.....	63
1.25.3	Allocation of resources.....	64
1.25.4	Data security.....	64
1.25.5	Ethical aspects	64
1.26	SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil organic carbon of Ireland.....	64
1.26.1	Data summary	64
1.26.2	FAIR data.....	64
1.26.3	Allocation of resources.....	66
1.26.4	Data security.....	66
1.26.5	Ethical aspects	66
1.27	SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil sealing of Ireland.....	66
1.27.1	Data summary	66
1.27.2	FAIR data.....	66
1.27.3	Allocation of resources.....	67
1.27.4	Data security.....	68
1.27.5	Ethical aspects	68
1.28	Map of SESs/STs Bundles for Europe (EU).....	68
1.28.1	Data summary	68
1.28.2	FAIR data.....	69
1.28.3	Allocation of resources.....	70
1.28.4	Data security.....	70
1.28.5	Ethical aspects	70
1.28.6	References.....	70
1.29	SERENA T3.2 - Map of Net Ecosystem Productivity of Emilia-Romagna Italy.....	71
1.29.1	Data summary	71
1.29.2	FAIR data.....	71
1.29.3	Allocation of resources.....	72
1.29.4	Data security.....	72
1.29.5	Ethical aspects	72
1.29.6	References.....	73
1.30	SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil organic carbon of Tuscany (Italy).....	73
1.30.1	Data summary	73
1.30.2	FAIR data.....	73

1.30.3	Allocation of resources	74
1.30.4	Data security.....	74
1.30.5	Ethical aspects	74
1.31	SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil sealing of Italy.....	75
1.31.1	Data summary	75
1.31.2	FAIR data.....	75
1.31.3	Allocation of resources.....	76
1.31.4	Data security.....	76
1.31.5	Ethical aspects	76
1.31.6	Other.....	76
1.32	SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil loss by water erosion of Tuscany (Italy)	76
1.32.1	Data summary	76
1.32.2	FAIR data.....	77
1.32.3	Allocation of resources.....	78
1.32.4	Data security.....	78
1.32.5	Ethical aspects	78
1.33	SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil mass not eroded of Tuscany (Italy)	78
1.33.1	Data summary	78
1.33.2	FAIR data.....	79
1.33.3	Allocation of resources.....	80
1.33.4	Data security.....	80
1.33.5	Ethical aspects	80
1.34	SERENA T3.2 - Maps of topsoil (0-30 cm) parameters of Tuscany (Italy).....	80
1.34.1	Data summary	80
1.34.2	FAIR data.....	81
1.34.3	Allocation of resources.....	82
1.34.4	Data security.....	82
1.34.5	Ethical aspects	82
1.35	SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil loss by water erosion of the Netherlands	82
1.35.1	Data summary	82
1.35.2	FAIR data.....	82
1.35.3	Allocation of resources.....	83
1.35.4	Data security.....	84
1.35.5	Ethical aspects	84
1.35.6	References.....	84

1.36	SERENA T3.2 - Map of Net Ecosystem Productivity of the Netherlands	84
1.36.1	Data summary	84
1.36.2	FAIR data.....	85
1.36.3	Allocation of resources.....	86
1.36.4	Data security.....	86
1.36.5	Ethical aspects	86
1.37	SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil sealing of the Netherlands.....	86
1.37.1	Data summary	86
1.37.2	FAIR data.....	87
1.37.3	Allocation of resources.....	88
1.37.4	Data security.....	88
1.37.5	Ethical aspects	88
1.38	SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil loss by water erosion of Poland	88
1.38.1	Data summary	88
1.38.2	FAIR data.....	88
1.38.3	Allocation of resources.....	90
1.38.4	Data security.....	90
1.38.5	Ethical aspects	90
1.39	SERENA T3.4 - Map of Soil mass not eroded of Poland.....	90
1.39.1	Data summary	90
1.39.2	FAIR data.....	90
1.39.3	Allocation of resources.....	91
1.39.4	Data security.....	92
1.39.5	Ethical aspects	92
1.40	SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil organic carbon of Portugal	92
1.40.1	Data summary	92
1.40.2	FAIR data.....	92
1.40.3	Allocation of resources.....	93
1.40.4	Data security.....	93
1.40.5	Ethical aspects	94
1.41	SERENA T3.2 - Erosion Control map of Slovakia.....	94
1.41.1	Data summary	94
1.41.2	FAIR data.....	94
1.41.3	Allocation of resources.....	95
1.41.4	Data security.....	95

1.41.5	Ethical aspects	96
1.42	SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil loss by water erosion of Slovakia	96
1.42.1	Data summary	96
1.42.2	FAIR data.....	96
1.42.3	Allocation of resources.....	97
1.42.4	Data security.....	97
1.42.5	Ethical aspects	97
1.43	SERENA T3.2 - Evaluation of soil threats and ecosystem service evolution under climate, land use or management changes. Deliverable report 3.4 and literature review.....	98
1.43.1	Data summary	98
1.43.2	FAIR data.....	98
1.43.3	Allocation of resources.....	99
1.43.4	Data security.....	99
1.43.5	Ethical aspects	99
1.44	SERENA T4.2 - Extending LUCAS with Corine Land Cover	99
1.44.1	Data summary	99
1.44.2	FAIR data.....	100
1.44.3	Allocation of resources.....	100
1.44.4	Data security.....	100
1.44.5	Ethical aspects	101
1.45	SERENA T3.3 – Maps for Soil loss by water from climate change scenarios for Austria.....	101
1.45.1	Data summary	101
1.45.2	FAIR data.....	101
1.45.3	Allocation of resources.....	102
1.45.4	Data security.....	102
1.45.5	Ethical aspects	102
1.46	Map of soil organic carbon for France	103
1.46.1	Data summary	103
1.46.2	FAIR data.....	103
1.46.3	Allocation of resources.....	104
1.46.4	Data security.....	104
1.46.5	Ethical aspects	104
1.47	Literature review Task 3.3	104
1.47.1	Data summary	104
1.47.2	FAIR data.....	105

1.47.3	Allocation of resources	105
1.47.4	Data security.....	106
1.47.5	Ethical aspects	106
1.48	Soil based ecosystem services individual assessments and bundles results	106
1.48.1	Data summary	106
1.48.2	FAIR data.....	108
1.48.3	Data security.....	109
1.48.4	Ethical aspects	109
1.49	Soil threats individual assessments and bundles results for 2050 in Europe	109
1.49.1	Data summary	109
1.49.2	FAIR data.....	114
1.49.3	Allocation of resources.....	114
1.49.4	Data security.....	114
1.49.5	Ethical aspects	115
1.49.6	Reference	115
1.50	Net Ecosystem Productivity Cookbook	115
1.50.1	Data summary	115
1.50.2	FAIR data.....	116
1.50.3	Allocation of resources.....	116
1.50.4	Data security.....	116
1.50.5	Ethical aspects	116
1.50.6	References.....	117
1.51	Deliverable T2.2 soil threats and soil ecosystem services of interest in SERENA	117
1.51.1	Data summary	117
1.51.2	FAIR data.....	117
1.51.3	Allocation of resources.....	117
1.51.4	Data security.....	117
1.51.5	Ethical aspects	117
1.52	Map of SESs/STs Bundles of Emilia-Romagna, Italy	118
1.52.1	Data summary	118
1.52.2	FAIR data.....	119
1.52.3	Allocation of resources.....	120
1.52.4	Data security.....	120
1.52.5	Ethical aspects	120
1.52.6	References.....	120

1 Datasets management and description

1.1 SERENA T1.1 – Stakeholder database development

1.1.1 Objectives and Data Summary

The objective of Task 1.1 was to establish a cohort of stakeholders actively involved in co-creating and validating all outputs and products of the SERENA project. This entailed defining the specific requirements for engaging stakeholders in each SERENA task. A compiled list of stakeholder contacts is organized in a database format, ensuring accessibility for all project partners throughout the entirety of the SERENA project. This database serves as a centralized resource for effective communication and collaboration with stakeholders.

The SERENA stakeholder database is an excel file that comprise of approximately 231 contacts, with 174 contacts sourced from the National Communication Representatives' (NCRs) derived database, 52 contacts obtained from the generic multi-stakeholder database for science-to-policy interactions provided by EJP Soil WP8 and 5 contacts added during the final SERENA validation tasks by the project partners. This centralised document is to be considered a live document that can be improved by any partner in SERENA. We envisage constant participation throughout the course of the project with an increase of the engagement towards the end of the project where the products of SERENA will have to be validated by the stakeholder's group/s.

1.1.2 FAIR data

1.1.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

To comply with GDPR regulations, the Centralized Database is not openly shared with all partners but securely stored on the Teagasc server and under the control of Teagasc partners (WP1 co-lead and T1.1 lead). Access to this central database is assured for all project partners, however engagement activities are contingent upon stakeholder availability.

1.1.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

Access to the Stakeholder database by the SERENA partners requires the completion of:

1. **Data Request Form:** This form includes details of the researcher and their affiliated institute for which data access is sought. It also requires a brief explanation of the purpose for access and the specific characteristics of the requested data (e.g., stakeholder type, scale, etc.).
2. **Confidentiality Form:** This form is designed to adhere to the Data Protection Act, 2003 and reflects our commitment to maintaining confidentiality with respect to stakeholders participating in the project.

The conditions governing access and utilization of the supplied data are established, and all partners must acknowledge and sign these conditions:

- *Use of the data is confined to the research project described above (SERENA, WP and Task number).*
- *Access to the data is restricted to the persons listed on your request form.*
- *None of the data is to be removed from the location indicated above (temporary location in the host institution).*
- *None of the data is to be released to a third party on any grounds whatsoever.*
- *Individual raw data cannot be published or presented under any circumstances.*

- *On completion of the project listed above (Completion date of the Task to be indicated), all the data are to be deleted by you from every form of storage.*

The structured procedure to access the database is established and summarised in Figure 1. The Data Request Form and Confidentiality Form are accessible in the SERENA shared folder. These forms are required to be completed and emailed to the Teagasc partners, who oversee the database. Upon receiving the forms, a stakeholder contact extraction based on the specified request will be performed, and the query results will be sent via email to the respective project partner. It is the responsibility of the project partners to initiate contact with the obtained list and communicate the details for stakeholder engagement and specific requirements.

Figure 1. Procedure to access the database by the SERENA partners.

1.1.2.3 Making data interoperable:

The stakeholder database is preserved through backups and is hosted and curated by Teagasc. The database setup and maintenance, data downloading, quality checking, is also performed by Teagasc. Standardised vocabulary and metadata for all data is developed in advance and shared with the partners.

1.1.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The SERENA outputs will be enhanced and disseminated by the project consortium and third parties under predefined data sharing and reuse licences. In the case of the stakeholder contact database, personal data privacy is strictly protected, and no personal contact information will be ever shared. However, the reuse of the database, in compliance with these privacy safeguards, will be encouraged, following the procedure described above.

1.1.3 Allocation of resources

Teagasc is the primary data manager for the stakeholder database using existing ICT infrastructure and computer servers for this purpose.

1.1.4 Data security

Data are securely stored in the Teagasc server and are made available upon request and following the above-described procedure. Data security is maintained by Teagasc and is password protected. The complete and quality-controlled stakeholder database is permanently stored and documented as .csv files. Daily data backup working group servers and access to backup media are managed according to data access rules. Backups are stored in another location in the Teagasc server.

1.1.5 Ethical aspects

The proposed project does not involve any of the following ethical issues: human participants, human cells/tissues, human embryonic stem cells, clinical trials, collection of personal/private data, animal experimentation or the potential for military applications (dual-use technology).

1.1.6 Other

None

1.2 SERENA T1.2 – Survey Results – Alignment of Terminology

1.2.1 Data summary

The dataset was collected in an online survey asking for the level of agreement of stakeholders with given definitions for numerous soil management terms. A common understanding of used language is fundamental for jointly working towards sustainable soil management practices.

The major part of data was requested for in a 7-grade Likert scale, additional comments were allowed. No existing data was re-used. The number of addressed persons reached around 2000 all over Europe, the number of participants was nearly 500. A detailed description of the dataset, its origins, the used questionnaire and an extensive discussion of its utility are given in Weninger *et al.* (2024).

1.2.2 FAIR data

1.2.2.1 *Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:*

The dataset was published open access under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929611>. The published zip-folder contains the raw data and a metadata file explaining the abbreviations and the structure of the data file. In the same repository, a technical report is provided including further information about the dataset and its origins.

1.2.2.2 *Making data openly accessible:*

All data are provided in the open access repository as it was put into the survey. The survey was anonymized, no personal information was required. There are two .csv-files which are packed in a .zip-file, hence accessible with every kind of standard software.

1.2.2.3 *Making data interoperable:*

See explanations above – it's one data table, explained in the meta-data-file and easily operable without any special requirements.

1.2.2.4 *Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):*

Data is open for re-use on CC BY 4.0 licence as long as the repository zenodo.org exists.

1.2.3 Allocation of resources

Making the dataset accessible costed around 3 hours of working time, funded by the grant mentioned in the footnote.

1.2.4 Data security

For data security, the highly secure repository zenodo.org is used. There is a copy stored and available at the internal server system of the main authors. No sensitive data is included.

1.2.5 Ethical aspects

No ethical or legal issues impacting the data sharing.

1.2.6 Other

None

1.2.7 References

Weninger, T., Ramler, D. *et al.* 2024. Do we speak one language on the way to sustainable soil management in Europe? A terminology check via an EU-wide survey. *European Journal of Soil Science* 75:e13476, 15 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13476>

1.3 SERENA T1.4 – Definition of scenarios - Survey results

1.3.1 Data summary

The objective of Task 1.4 was to make stakeholders aware of general trends under different scenarios, and in encouraging cooperation in highlighting the most relevant trends for further development. To achieve this aim, a questionnaire was produced and distributed to stakeholders.

To create the questionnaire, it was decided to use a semi-structured interview. The format of the survey was as follows:

- At the beginning of the questionnaire, an introduction was included, to explain the reason and the aim of the survey.
- To get deeper insights about drivers and scenarios of change, the first part of the survey included some questions about the stakeholder's opinion on the importance of SESs, ST and drivers of change, followed by questions about their agreement on strategies and practices to adopt or avoid selected scenarios of change. Towards the end of the survey, questions related to the stakeholder's willingness or ability to adapt to environmental changes by modifying policies or practices.
- A Likert scale approach with a rating scheme of four-point scales was chosen.
- The list of choices included responses relating to agreement (strongly disagree, somewhat disagree, somewhat agree, strongly agree), importance (not important, slightly important, Important, very important), and value (very low, low, high, very high).
- The questionnaire was prepared in English and then translated into 13 languages thanks to the support of SERENA partners: Dutch, Lithuanian, Portuguese, Polish, Latvian, Hungarian, French, Estonian, Slovak, Spanish, Norwegian, German, and Italian.
- The online platform Google Forms was used to upload the questionnaires. The questionnaire was distributed to stakeholders whose names and emails were provided by the SERENA Stakeholder Database and the Policy Stakeholders contact list of EJP SOIL WP8. Others were contacted by the National Communication Representatives and during meetings held in Italy and Austria; or thanks to the collaboration of the national soil science societies.
- A total of 379 filled questionnaires from 15 countries were gathered and analysed. The results were collected in a .xlsx file

1.3.2 FAIR data

1.3.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (xlsx file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_Task1.4.xlsx") is available in the Zenodo repository which provides it a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13982874>). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "stakeholders", "climate change", "land use", "land cover", "land management", "demographic trends.", "scenario". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created in .txt format. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Contact
- Links
- History/version

1.3.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil community. It complies with the Zenodo's platform, and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project.

The dataset uses an xlsx format that can be open in several applications both open-source and proprietary.

1.3.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a xlsx file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms.

1.3.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY 4.0).

1.3.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.3.4 Data security

Regarding GDPR issues, the survey was anonymized, no personal information was required.

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.3.5 Ethical aspects

The data are not restricted by legal and ethical issues.

1.3.6 Other

None.

1.4 SERENA T3.1 – Currently available assessments of soil threats and ecosystem services: data, metadata, and methodologies (D3.1.1) and Critical analysis of the experiences at member state level (D3.2v1)

1.4.1 Data summary

The objectives of T3.1 were to:

- collect information about approaches at different spatial scales developed by the member states to evaluate soil threats, soil-based ecosystem services and bundles (→ D3.1.1) and
- compare these approaches concerning their integration and harmonization (→ D3.2v1).

D3.1.1: Data was collected using a template to obtain all relevant information from the participating member states. This information included for each relevant case study (national or regional level):

- the indicator(s) used (including metrics),
- the primary data used (also sources and availability),
- the methods applied so that it can be easily understood what was done, and
- the main results such as maps and/or tables.

It was provided by 14 out of 16 member states on five soil threats (soil organic carbon loss, soil erosion, soil compaction, nutrient imbalance, and soil sealing) and four soil-based ecosystem services (greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration, hydrological control, primary/biomass production, and erosion control).

D3.2v1: The information collected in D3.1.1, i.e., the indicators, methods and data used (including data availability), was compared to identify differences and similarities between the assessments of the different member states as well as the need for harmonization, for each studied soil threat and soil-based ecosystem service. This was performed at the national level, but also on the regional scale. The critical analysis was limited to soil threats and soil-based ecosystem services which were also considered by other work packages/tasks. The four soil threats common to all were:

- soil organic carbon loss
- soil erosion
- soil compaction and
- soil sealing.

The four soil-based ecosystem services covered were the same as listed above.

1.4.2 FAIR data

1.4.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset was published open access under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10402477> (D3.1.1) and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12546320> (D3.2v1). The published report D3.1.1 contains all case studies provided.

The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, deliverable number, work package, and task: “SERENA” “EJPSoil”, “D3.1.1” or “D3.2v1”, “WP3”, Task 3.1”. The soil threats and soil-based ecosystem services were added as specific tags of the dataset.

1.4.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP Soil and EJP Soil SERENA communities and is open access. All data are provided as it was put the report D3.1.1. The report D3.2v1 is a summary and synthesis based on the data collected in D3.1.1.

1.4.2.3 Making data interoperable:

The dataset does not contain raw or primary data. It is a collection (with associated metadata) of already existing datasets owned and managed by the participating member states.

1.4.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

Data is open for re-use under CC BY 4.0 as long as the repository zenodo.org exists.

1.4.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.4.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.4.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.4.6 Other

None

1.5 SERENA T3.1 – Currently available assessments of soil threats and ecosystem services: data, metadata, and methodologies - update (D3.1.2)

and Critical analysis of the experiences at member state level - extension (D3.2v2)

1.5.1 Data summary

The objectives of T3.1 were to:

- collect information about approaches at different spatial scales developed by the member states to evaluate soil threats, soil-based ecosystem services and bundles (→ D3.1.1) and
- compare these approaches concerning their integration and harmonization (→ D3.2v1).

D3.1.2: Data was collected using a template to obtain all relevant information from the participating member states. This information included for each relevant case study (national or regional level)

- the indicator(s) used (including metrics),
- the primary data used (also sources and availability),
- the methods applied so that it can be easily understood what was done, and
- the main results such as maps and/or tables.

It was provided by 14 out of 16 member states on five soil threats (loss of diversity, soil acidification, soil contamination, waterlogging, and salinization) and three soil-based ecosystem services (habitat for biodiversity, environmental pollution control, and pest and disease control).

D3.2v2: The information collected in D3.1.2, i.e., the indicators, methods and data used (including data availability), was compared to identify differences and similarities between the assessments of the different member states as well as the need for harmonization, for each studied soil threat and soil-based ecosystem service. This was performed at the national level. Assessments at the regional level were considered only if none was available for the national scale. Seven soil threats were considered – in addition to the five listed above for D3.1.2 nutrient imbalance and soil drought. The three soil-based ecosystem services covered were the same as listed above.

1.5.2 FAIR data

1.5.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset was published open access under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10402591> (D3.1.2) and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12547273> (D3.2v2). The published report D3.1.2 contains all case studies provided.

The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, deliverable number, work package, and task: “SERENA” “EJPSoil”, “D3.1.2” or “D3.2v2”, “WP3”, Task 3.1”. The soil threats and soil-based ecosystem services were added as specific tags of the dataset.

1.5.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP Soil and EJP Soil SERENA communities and is open access. All data is provided as it was put the report D3.1.2. The report D3.2v2 is a summary and synthesis based on the data collected in D3.1.1 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10402478>; nutrient imbalance) and D3.1.2.

1.5.2.3 Making data interoperable:

The dataset does not contain raw or primary data. It is a collection (with associated metadata) of already existing datasets owned and managed by the participating member states.

1.5.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

Data is open for re-use under CC BY 4.0 as long as the repository zenodo.org exists.

1.5.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.5.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.5.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.5.6 Other

None

1.6 SERENA T3.2 - Map of Scenarios of Soil Threats and Soil Ecosystem Services in AT

1.6.1 Data summary

The presented dataset corresponds to an asset of Austrian regional maps of results from the simulation of climate and management scenarios by the process-based LandscapeDNDC model. The maps present mean annual N₂O emissions, soil carbon stocks, NO₃⁻ leaching and yield production of representative grassland soils in the regions. This dataset is part of “D3.4 Evaluation of soil threats and ecosystem service evolution under climate, land use or management changes” (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13945384>) and cover only parts of the assessed soil threats and ecosystem services in representative grassland regions in Austria.

1.6.2 FAIR data

1.6.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset “D3.4_Map of Scenarios of Soil Threats and Soil Ecosystem Services in AT_zip.zip” (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13912843>) is a collection containing the datasets of

- SERENA_AT_grassland_N2O.gpkg
- SERENA_AT_grassland_NO3.gpkg
- SERENA_AT_grassland_SOC.gpkg
- SERENA_AT_grassland_yield.gpkg

as well as the associated metadata. The dataset is available in the general science repository of Zenodo after October 2025 (restricted due to plans of publication). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA. The keywords include “SERENA”, “Horizon 2020 grant number 862695”, deliverable number “D3.4” and specific tags of the dataset: “regional”, “grassland”, “Austria”.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema, and it is part of the dataset file properties.

1.6.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13912843>). It complies with the Zenodo’s platform, and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open (e.g., QGIS) and propriety (ArcGIS).

1.6.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geopackage file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage.

1.6.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the resources LandscapeDNDC (<https://ldndc.imk-ifu.kit.edu/>) and eBod (<https://bodenkarte.at>).

1.6.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.6.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.6.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.7 SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil sealing of Austria

1.7.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil Sealing cookbook. For Austria, the application was carried out at regional scale.

The map of soil sealing (soil threat) was based on classification of multitemporal satellite images and photointerpretation. The methodology uses vegetation and backscatter indices calculated over time series of images, and decision rules. The semi-automatic classification supports the subsequent photointerpretation phase based on national orthophotos and other free VHR satellite images (e.g. through Google Earth or Bing services). The final maps are the product of a binary classification (sealed/not-sealed) having 10 m spatial resolution

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. The selected indicator was degree of soil sealing. By evaluating this degree at two moments in time, the change in soil sealing can be determined.

To create the soil sealing map, we used Sentinel-1 C-band synthetic aperture radar imaging and Sentinel-2 Multispectral Instrument (MSI) (<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>) for the semi-automatic classification, and Google Earth images for the photointerpretation.

Delivered map was prepared in the GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 10 m.

1.7.2 FAIR data

1.7.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (GeoTIFF file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_AT_SOILSEALING_SEALINGDEGREE.gpkg") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969874>) with a DOI identifier. The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "soil sealing", "remote sensing", "satellite images", "photointerpretation", "AUSTRIA". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema in .txt format, and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.

- Contact

1.7.2.2 *Making data openly accessible:*

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. It complies with the Zenodo's platform, and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (gpkg) that can be open in several GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.7.2.3 *Making data interoperable:*

As stated, the dataset is provided as a gpkg file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil sealing research.

1.7.2.4 *Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):*

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA Soil Sealing cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Italy. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.7.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.7.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.7.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.8 SERENA T3.3 - Literature review

1.8.1 Data summary

We reviewed existing modelling studies from all over the world focusing on scenario analyses of SES and ST including climate change, land use change and management scenarios. A publication has been submitted to "Science of the total environment" and is currently being reviewed. The title of the manuscript is: Assessing and mapping soil ecosystem services and soil threats changes in agroecosystems through scenario-based approaches – a systematic review.

Work was split between various authors. All Co-authors that are mentioned in the first page were working on either one or more SES or one ST. Excel sheets were prepared by INRAE and BFW to ensure the comparability of results that members extracted from the papers found. Literature search was done in Scopus and Web of Science. The aim of the literature review was mainly to:

- understand how different drivers of global change are most commonly studied in scientific literature.
- identify which SES and ST are most commonly studied and how they are assessed and mapped in scenario-based approaches.
- Finally, provide a preliminary discussion on how soil properties are represented in these scenario-based approaches.

After screening the Web and sorting out unusable papers we found 230 published articles related to 7 SES and 10 ST.

1.8.2 FAIR data

1.8.2.1 *Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:*

The dataset (Excel table with all used papers and a Zotero list with all papers that were used for the literature review and for the above-mentioned publication) is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969536>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (National SoilHUBS: Assessment of (bundles of) Soil functions/threats/ecosystem services at different scales). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in the SERENA community. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "review", "global", "literature". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

1.8.2.2 *Making data openly accessible:*

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. It complies with the Zenodo's platform, and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset is an excel table and a Zotero file.

The paper will be uploaded as soon as it is accepted for publication.

1.8.2.3 *Making data interoperable:*

As stated, the dataset is provided as Excel file and as Zotero literature list. The format is interoperable across software and platforms.

1.8.2.4 *Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):*

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The extracted data comes from the papers that were used for the literature review. Data were later on harmonized to make it comparable and to be sure that the same wording is used in each column.

1.8.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.8.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.8.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.9 SERENA T3.3 - SERENA EJPSOIL France climatic and agricultural change modelling datasets

1.9.1 Data summary

Data have been generated to model the agricultural system according to a range of agricultural and climate scenarios under a variety of soil across 2 study sites.

The data generation aims to explore the effects of climate change according to different climate scenarios up to 2050, and to understand the resistance of soils in response to climate change and different types of agricultural management. In addition, it aims to understand the relationships between Soil Ecosystem Services (SESS), and the main factors influencing variations in SESS.

Data were generated as .csv files for each point of the simulation model for each climate model, for each scenario, for each study site.

Naizin's soil data come from Walter *et al.* (1993, 1996, 1998) and Saclay's from Scammacca *et al.* (2023). Climatic data were obtained from SAFRAN climatic data provided by Météo-France and were downloaded via the SICLIMA platform developed by AgroClim-INRAE. Plants and fertilizers data come from the integrated dataset of STICS. All input data are available as part of this dataset.

The data have been produced by the SERENA team WP3.3 France using JAVA-STICS 10.0.0 model and the STICSOnR package, using the input files specified in the data.

Expected size is about 540 Mo.

The produced data are exploratory and will support soil and agricultural future research using SES and climatic evolution.

1.9.2 FAIR data

1.9.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The naming of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA project (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The provision of metadata complies with the Zenodo repository which uses metadata standards (DataCite), requires keywords linked to standard vocabularies, and allows versioning. The repository uses the DOI as persistent identifier. The dataset consists of a single version since, as there are no upgradeable versions of the dataset. It will be downloadable in the EJP Soil SERENA community in a csv format. A Readme file will be also available in the EJP Soil SERENA community describing the different files using the template suggested by the repository.

1.9.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The datasets were uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP Soil SERENA and EJP Soil communities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14000971> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14000724>). They comply with the Zenodo's platform, and they follow the information agreed at final meeting of the project (see previous section).

The data could be accessed using any spreadsheet software. In addition, all input files used by the model in this study will be available. JAVA-STICS is available after registering on the STICS website <https://stics.inrae.fr/eng/download>.

1.9.2.3 Making data interoperable:

Results data are in the form of .csv files which can be accessed using any spreadsheet software. Input data are specific to the STICS model and are .xml files that do not require special software to open.

1.9.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

If data can be made openly accessible, they will be available for re-use at the end of the project after the embargo period.

1.9.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate them. Once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated in the long term.

1.9.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.9.5 Ethical aspects

The data are not restricted by legal and ethical issues as long as they are generated in the context of research on biophysical and ecological indicators.

1.9.6 References

Scammacca, O., Sauzet, O., Michelin, J., Choquet, P., Garnier, P., Gabrielle, B., Baveye, P.C., Montagne, D. 2023 - Effect of spatial scale of soil data on estimates of soil ecosystem services: Case study in 100 km² area in France. *European Journal of Soil Science*, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13359>

Walter C, Gourru M and Nicolas JM (1993) Carte des sols du bassin versant de Naizin à l'échelle de 1/10000. Document ENSA-INRA Rennes, Laboratoire de Science du Sol. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13359>

Walter, C., Curmi, P., Gascuel-Oudou, C. 1996 - Pertinence du découpage pédologique pour l'estimation spatiale des propriétés physiques du sol. Validation à l'échelle d'un bassin versant. *In Étude des Phénomènes Spatiaux en agriculture, Christophe, Lardon et Monestiez (Eds), La Rochelle, 1995/12/06-08, INRA Éditions, Colloques de l'INRA (FRA), n. 78, 97-110.*

Walter, C., Curmi, P. 1998 - Les sols du bassin versant du Coetdan : organisation, variabilité spatiale et cartographie. In : CHEVERRY C. (Éditeur). - Agriculture intensive et qualité des eaux. INRA Éditions ; collection Science Update, 85-105.

1.10 SERENA T3.2 - SERENA EJPSOIL cookbook map of soil erosion risk of Flanders (Belgium): SERENA_EJPSOIL_BE_Flanders_EROSION_SOILLOSS_cookbook

1.10.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA soil erosion cookbook. For Belgium, the application was carried out at regional scale for the Flanders region.

The dataset was mainly produced to test the methodology of the SERENA soil erosion cookbook. And serve as a proof of concept for the cookbook.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats.

To create the soil erosion map, we used several publicly available datasets.

The following auxiliary data was used:

- K-Factor
- Land-Cover Map
- Long-term 30-year averaged monthly rainfall
- LS-Factor

The delivered map was prepared in the GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 5 m.

The dataset will be mostly useful as a reference result for actors that want to learn to implement the part of the soil erosion cookbook of SERENA dealing with the creation of an erosion map. It has limited use as an erosion map for Flanders because a more detailed and accurate map exists for Flanders based on regional covariates.

1.10.2 FAIR data

1.10.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (GeoTIFF file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_BE_Flanders_EROSION_SOILLOSS_cookbookEOSION.tiff") is available through the DOV services (a persistent repository for soil and subsoil scientific and government data) and is provided with metadata and a persistent URI (<https://www.dov.vlaanderen.be/geonetwork/srv/dut/catalog.search#/metadata/37337449-8bee-420e-9943-81f074c4cbe8>). A metadata record referring to this publication is available in the general science repository of Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13993234>), and is provided with a DOI identifier. This two-pronged approach allows the data to both become findable in open science and open data repositories (Flemish, national and European). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "EROSION", "Geostatistics", "BELGIUM (FLANDERS)". Besides these keywords standard keywords and their accompanying thesauri for the DOV publications are used. The dataset consists of a single version since the project has come to an end and only one version of the dataset has been created during the project. The standards for the

creation of metadata under the INSPIRE directive (ISO/TS 19139:2007) follow as is standard practice at DOV.

A metadata schema was created and includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keywords: SERENA, DOV, INSPIRE/HVD?
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc. zie DOV metadata
- Contact: DOV contactgegevens
- Links: rapport, services
- History/version: version 1.0.0, lineage information, ...
- Authors and contact: zie voorgaande contactgegevens

1.10.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset is published through DOV and made available through its metadata record in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. The dataset is published as open data.

The dataset uses an open, platform-independent data format (GeoTIFF) and standardized and open OGC services (WMS, WCS) that can be opened and accessed in a number of commonly used GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS) and using common scripting and programming languages (Python, R, Java; ...).

1.10.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a GeoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms.

1.10.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Flemish model licence for free re-use, which is a CC BY 3.0 compatible licence (Modellicentie Gratis Hergebruik | Vlaanderen.be) The data comes from applying the SERENA soil erosion cookbook based on the most up to date and accurate datasets available for Flanders (Belgium).

There will be no embargo applied to the publication of the data and there will be no re-use restrictions on the data except for the attribution requirement of the CC BY licence.

The quality assurance will be limited to the quality assurance that is part of the application of the SERENA soil erosion cookbook. DOV will publish the data AS IS without warranties, no ongoing quality assurance will be performed, unless related to keeping the publication in compliance with the FAIR principles.

Re-usability of the data will be at the minimum ensured by DOV until a new better dataset becomes available on DOV fully replacing this one or until the data reusability needs to be ensured by EJP SOIL agreements/Horizon 2020 requirements. The applicable time period will be whichever is longest. At a yet undetermined time after this period, re-usability could decrease somewhat due to the dataset being moved from the standard DOV (active and archival) publication to full archiving because the dataset has become fully deprecated and is superseded in its usability by other products.

1.10.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation will be borne by the Flemish Government, particularly the Department of Environment and Spatial Development (DOMG) and the interagency cooperation Databank Ondergrond Vlaanderen (DOV). The cost to make the data FAIR and to publish it will be covered using EJP SOIL budget (3 person days). The cost of maintaining the FAIR publication and the used infrastructure (except for Zenodo) will be covered by the Flemish government (estimated as 0.5-person day a year and the cost of maintaining the publication of the DOV services at low to medium load). DOV will maintain the publication of the dataset as part as its duty to be a custodian of soil and subsoil in Flanders. DOV will ensure the persistency of the dataset and maintain the relevant metadata record on Zenodo. The dataset will eventually also become part of the archive of the Flemish government. Given that the dataset will not be updated after the SERENA project it will only get limited maintenance focusing on maintaining its persistence and availability.

1.10.4 Data security

The dataset is not considered to be sensitive data and will be published using the standard practices and security of open data at DOV.

The data will become part of the standard practices for backups and archiving at DOV and the Flemish department OMG. Ensuring that in the event or an unforeseen event the data will remain recoverable and a copy of the data will according to the relevant procedures be archived in the archive of the Flemish government.

1.10.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.10.6 Other

- DOV: Welkom bij Databank Ondergrond Vlaanderen | DOV
- Flemish government digital archive: Digitaal Archief Vlaanderen | Vlaanderen.be

1.11 SERENA T3.2 - SERENA EJPSOIL cookbook map of soil organic carbon of Flanders (Belgium): SERENA_EJPSOIL_BE_Flanders_SOCLOSS_SOC_0-20cm_cookbook

1.11.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA SOC loss cookbook. For Belgium, the application was carried out at regional scale for the Flanders region.

The dataset was mainly produced to test the methodology of the SERENA SOC loss cookbook. And serve as a proof of concept for the cookbook.

The map of soil organic carbon (soil threat) was based on digital mapping according to the method used in the EJP SOIL project WP6: Digital soil mapping approach with random forest using ISRIC workflow seedling.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil organic carbon concentration was used as an indicator for soil organic carbon loss (ST).

To create the soil organic carbon concentration map, we used soil organic carbon data of the regional soil organic carbon monitoring network Cmon in Flanders (0-10 and 10-30 cm soil layer). The soil organic carbon concentration of the 0-20 cm was derived from the 0-10 and 10-30 cm data.

The following auxiliary data was used:

- Digitale bodemkaart van het Vlaams Gewest: bodemtypes
- Regional climate data
- Landgebruik - Vlaanderen - toestand 2022
- Tertiair geologische kaart (1/50.000)
- Bodembedekkingskaart (BBK), 1m resolutie, opname 2021
- WRB Soil Units 40k: Bodemkaart van het Vlaamse Gewest volgens het internationale bodemclassificatiesysteem World Reference Base op schaal 1:40.000
- Digitaal Hoogtemodel Vlaanderen II, DSM, raster, 1 m

The delivered map was prepared in the GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 100 m.

The dataset will be mostly useful as a reference result for actors that want to learn to implement the part of the soil organic carbon loss cookbook of SERENA dealing with the creation of a SOC concentration map. It can have limited use as an interim SOC concentration map for Flanders until a better map becomes available using an optimised methodology and/or new data from the regional soil organic carbon monitoring network that was not yet available when this map was created.

1.11.2 FAIR data

1.11.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (GeoTIFF file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_BE_Flanders_SOCLOSS_SOC_0-20cm_cookbook.tiff") is available through the DOV services (a persistent repository for soil and subsoil scientific and government data) and is provided with metadata and a persistent URI (<https://www.dov.vlaanderen.be/geonetwork/srv/dut/catalog.search#/metadata/37337449-8bee-420e-9943-81f074c4cbe8>). A metadata record referring to this publication is available in the general science repository of Zenodo, and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13981884>). This two-pronged approach allows the data to both become findable in open science and open data repositories (Flemish, national and European). The

name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "SOCLOSS", "SOC", "Geostatistics", "BELGIUM (FLANDERS)". Besides these keywords standard keywords and their accompanying thesauri for the DOV publications are used. The dataset consists of a single version since the project has come to an end and only one version of the dataset has been created during the project. The standards for the creation of metadata under the INSPIRE directive (ISO/TS 19139:2007) follow as is standard practice at DOV.

A metadata schema will be created and includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keywords: SERENA, DOV, INSPIRE/HVD?
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc. zie DOV metadata
- Contact: DOV contactgegevens
- Links: rapport, services
- History/version: version 1.0.0, lineage information, ...
- Authors and contact: zie voorgaande contactgegevens

1.11.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset will be published through DOV and made available through its metadata record in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. The data will be published as open data.

The dataset uses an open, platform-independent data format (GeoTIFF) and standardized and open OGC services (WMS, WCS) that can be opened and accessed in a number of commonly used GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS) and using common scripting and programming languages (Python, R, Java; ...).

1.11.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a GeoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms.

1.11.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence will be the Flemish model licence for free re-use, which is a CC BY 3.0 compatible licence (Modellicentie Gratis Hergebruik | Vlaanderen.be) The data comes from applying the SERENA SOC loss cookbook based on the most up to date and accurate datasets available for Flanders (Belgium).

There will be no embargo applied to the publication of the data and there will be no re-use restrictions on the data except for the attribution requirement of the CC BY licence.

The quality assurance will be limited to the quality assurance that is part of the application of the SERENA SOC loss cookbook. DOV will publish the data AS IS without warranties, no ongoing quality assurance will be performed, unless related to keeping the publication in compliance with the FAIR principles.

Re-usability of the data will be at the minimum ensured by DOV until a new better dataset becomes available on DOV fully replacing this one or until the data reusability needs to be ensured by EJP SOIL agreements/Horizon 2020 requirements. The applicable time period will be whichever is longest. At a yet undetermined time after this period, re-usability could decrease somewhat due to the dataset being moved from the standard DOV (active and archival) publication to full archiving because the dataset has become fully deprecated and is superseded in its usability by other products.

1.11.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation will be borne by the Flemish Government, particularly the Department of Environment and Spatial Development (DOMG) and the interagency cooperation Databank Ondergrond Vlaanderen (DOV). The cost to make the data FAIR and to publish it will be covered using EJP SOIL budget (3 person days). The cost of maintaining the FAIR publication and the used infrastructure (except for Zenodo) will be covered by the Flemish government (estimated as 0.5-person day a year and the cost of maintaining the publication of the DOV services at low to medium load). DOV will maintain the publication of the dataset as part as its duty to be a custodian of soil and subsoil in Flanders. DOV will ensure the persistency of the dataset and maintain the relevant metadata record on Zenodo. The dataset will eventually also become part of the archive of the Flemish government. Given that the dataset will not be updated after the SERENA project it will only get limited maintenance focusing on maintaining its persistence and availability.

1.11.4 Data security

The dataset is not considered to be sensitive data and will be published using the standard practices and security of open data at DOV.

The data will become part of the standard practices for backups and archiving at DOV and the Flemish department OMG. Ensuring that in the event or an unforeseen event the data will remain recoverable, and a copy of the data will according to the relevant procedures be archived in the archive of the Flemish government.

1.11.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.11.6 Other

- DOV: Welkom bij Databank Ondergrond Vlaanderen | DOV
- Flemish government digital archive: Digitaal Archief Vlaanderen | Vlaanderen.be

1.12 SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil sealing of Flanders (Belgium): SERENA_EJPSOIL_BE_Flanders_SOILSEALING_SEALINGDEGREE

1.12.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the Level 2 methodology of the SERENA soil sealing cookbook. For Belgium, the application was carried out at the regional scale for the Flanders region.

The automatically generated yearly soil sealing maps combine “known” sealing from administrative databases (buildings and transport infrastructure) with modelled sealing based on artificial intelligence. Administrative databases do not (adequately) cover parking lots, private driveways and garden terraces, which are a substantial part of the sealed area in Flanders. Hence, a machine learning model was built for deriving this remaining sealing from aerial imagery. For this purpose, an assessor manually labelled the sealed parts on a subset of the images. Based on this training set, a convolutional neural network model was used to produce a sealing probability map, which was converted to a binary modelled sealing map. Finally, a continuity correction was applied to ensure a temporally consistent result across the yearly maps.

The objective of the SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. The selected indicator was the degree of soil sealing. By evaluating this degree at two moments in time, the change in soil sealing can be determined.

The following data were used:

- Large-scale Reference Database (*Grootschalig Referentiebestand* or *Basiskaart*), the digital topographic reference map for Flanders (vector)
- Medium-scale annual winter aerial images of Flanders (15 or 25 cm raster resolution)

The delivered maps were prepared in the GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 1 m.

The delivered data were validated by spatial planners and policy makers in Flanders in October 2024.

1.12.2 FAIR data

1.12.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The GeoTIFF dataset file “SERENA_EJPSOIL_BE_Flanders_SOILSEALING_SEALINGDEGREE.tiff” is available through the Geopunt services (a persistent repository for geographical scientific and government data) and will be provided with metadata and a persistent URI (https://www.vlaanderen.be/datavindplaats/catalogus?domain.CONTAINS_ANY=Geografisch&q.LIKE=jaarbak&order_relevance=asc). A metadata record referring to this publication is available in the general science repository of Zenodo and will be provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14008412>). This two-pronged approach allows the data to both become findable in open science and open data repositories (Flemish, national and European).

The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: “SERENA”, “EJP-SOIL”, “soil sealing”, “remote sensing”, “aerial images”, “photointerpretation” and “BELGIUM (FLANDERS)”. Besides these keywords, standard keywords and their accompanying thesauri for the Geopunt publications are used.

The dataset consists of a separate dataset per year since 2013, which might be subject to upgrades in the future.

A metadata schema will be created and includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links: rapport, services
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.12.2.2 Making data openly accessible

The dataset is published through Geopunt and made available through its metadata record in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. The data will be published as open data.

The dataset uses an open, platform-independent data format (GeoTIFF) and standardized and open OGC services (WMS, WCS) that can be opened and accessed in a number of commonly used GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS) and using common scripting and programming languages (Python, R, Java ...).

1.12.2.3 Making data interoperable

As stated, the dataset is provided as a GeoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil sealing research.

1.12.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

The dataset licence will be the Flemish model licence for free re-use, which is a CC BY 3.0 compatible licence (Modellicentie Gratis Hergebruik | Vlaanderen.be). The data comes from applying the SERENA soil sealing cookbook based on the most up-to-date and accurate datasets available for Flanders (Belgium). No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.12.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation will be borne by the Flemish Government, particularly the Department of Environment and Spatial Development (DOMG). The cost of publishing and maintaining the FAIR publication and the used infrastructure (except for Zenodo) will be covered by the Flemish government (estimated as 3 person days a year). Geopunt will maintain the publication of the dataset as part as its duty to be a custodian of geographical open data in Flanders. It will ensure the persistency of the dataset and maintain the relevant metadata record on Zenodo. The dataset will eventually also become part of the archive of the Flemish government.

1.12.4 Data security

The dataset is not considered to be sensitive data and will be published using the standard practices and security of open data at Geopunt.

The data will become part of the standard practices for backups and archiving at Geopunt and the Flemish DOMG, ensuring that in the event of an unforeseen event the data will remain recoverable,

and a copy of the data will be archived by the Flemish government according to the relevant procedures.

1.12.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.13 SERENA T3.2 - Map of SESs/STs Bundles for Czechia (EU)

1.13.1 Data summary

The present dataset corresponds to a map of soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats for Czechia. The map is the result of applying the bundles cookbook developed in SERENA/EJP-Soil to the area of interest (AOI) input data. The resulting bundles are clusters of SESs/STs where the intra-cluster variability is lower than the inter-cluster variability in the mean values of the selected SESs/STs to identify the bundles.

SERENA had, among others, the objective of developing methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats and their bundles.

For this purpose, the bundles in the present geodatasets were determined from 3 spatially-explicit datasets to which the bundles cookbook was applied within the AOI: (1) eroded soil organic carbon (ESDAC Pan-European SOC stock of agricultural soils dataset, published in Lugato *et al.* 2016), (2) biomass production (ESDAC Soil Biomass Productivity maps of grasslands and pasture, of croplands and of forest areas in the European Union dataset, published in Tóth *et al.* 2013), and (3) water erosion (ESDAC Multiple concurrent soil erosion processes dataset, published in Borrelli *et al.* 2022).

The 4 geodatasets of bundles are in vector format and are:

Bundles' geodataset name	Description	Size
SERENA_EJPSoil_Bundles_cookbook_CZmap.tif	Bundle map in which the input geodata was not filled for spatial gaps, variables are min-max-scaled and the extent is the Czechia	201.2 Mb

Although the dataset needs further validation, it is useful as a research tool to investigate co-occurrence of SESs and STs for the SERENA consortium and other researchers.

1.13.2 FAIR data

1.13.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The geodatasets (geopackage files: SERENA_EJPSoil_Bundles_cookbook_CZmap.tif) are available in the general science repository Zenodo which will provide a DOI identifier. The name of the datasets

follows the convention agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (SERENA_EJPSoil_Bundles_cookbook_CZmap). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include specific tags of the dataset: "soil-based ecosystem services co-occurrence", "soil threats co-occurrence", "soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats bundles", "European Union". The dataset correspond to single versions since there are no upgradable versions to the datasets in mind.

The project information will be also indicated in the metadata of the dataset: SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema, and is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version

1.13.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset will be uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP-Soil Serena community. It will comply with the Zenodo's platform, and it will follow the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data are open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload, yet a 6-months period of embargo will apply in view of potential publications.

1.13.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a Geotif file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in ecosystem services bundles research.

1.13.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence will be the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The data comes from applying the SERENA bundles cookbook. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.13.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.13.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.13.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.13.6 References

Borrelli, P., Panagos, P., Alewell, C., Ballabio, C., de Oliveira Fagundes, H., Haregeweyn, N., Lugato, E., Maerker, M., Poesen, J., Vanmaercke, M. and Robinson, D.A., 2022. Policy implications of multiple concurrent soil erosion processes in European farmland. *Nature Sustainability*. DOI: 10.1038/s41893-022-00988-4.

Lugato, E., Paustian, K., Panagos, P., Jones, A., Borrelli, P., 2016. Quantifying the erosion effect on current carbon budget of European agricultural soils at high spatial resolution. *Global Change Biology* (2016), 22(5), 1976–1984, <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13198>

Tóth, G., Gardi, C., Bódis, K., Ivits, É., Aksoy, E., Jones, A., Jeffrey, S., Petursdottir, T. and Montanarella, L., 2013. Continental-scale assessment of provisioning soil functions in Europe. *Ecological Processes*, 2, pp.1-18.

1.14 SERENA T3.2 - Map of Net Ecosystem Productivity of Moravia region-Czechia

1.14.1 Data summary

The present dataset corresponds to a map of Net Ecosystem Productivity (NEP) for Moravia region in Czechia classified as wheat by the Eurocrop 2028 spatial product (d'Andrimont *et al.* 2021). The map is the result of applying the NEP cookbook developed in SERENA/EJP-Soil to the area of interest (AOI) input data. NEP is expressed for a single 8-day period in early summer as it is the date with the highest value. The NEP value is a 2010-2014 average for the particular 8-day period. The data description document of the cookbook (hereafter “GHG cookbook”) itself corresponds to another document of the SERENA project.

SERENA had, among others, the objective of developing methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. NEP was used as an indicator of greenhouse gases and climate regulation supported by soils.

For this purpose, NEP was calculated from (data origin) 4 spatially-explicit datasets to which the GHG cookbook was applied within the AOI: (1) maximum monthly air temperature from WorldClimate, (2) minimum monthly air temperature from WorldClimate, (3) MODIS MOD17A2HGF collection, and (4) daily soil moisture data derived from Zhang *et al.* (2023). (5) The Eurocrop 2018 database was used to filter the spatialisation of the indicator to wheat areas, and (6) the AOI border.

The NEP map for Moravia region is 146 Mb.

Although the dataset needs further validation, it is useful as a research tool to investigate CO2 fluxes in the region for the SERENA consortium and other researchers.

1.14.2 FAIR data

1.14.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geopackage file: “SERENA_EJPSOIL_CZ_GHG_NEP.gpkg”) is available in the general science repository Zenodo which provides a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14054263>). The name of the dataset follows the convention agreed upon in SERENA’s WP3 (project_country_soilecosystem_service_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include specific tags of the dataset: “greenhouse gases and climate regulation indicators”, “net ecosystem productivity”, “Moravia-region, Czechia”. The dataset consists in a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset in mind.

The project information will be also indicated in the metadata of the dataset: SERENA project, grant agreement No. 862695.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema, and is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version

1.14.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP-Soil Serena community. It complies with the Zenodo’s platform, and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data are open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload, yet a 6-months period of embargo will apply in view of potential publications.

1.14.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geopackage file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in carbon fluxes research.

1.14.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The data comes from applying the SERENA GHG cookbook which applied different filters to eliminate NEP values inconsistencies. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.14.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.14.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.14.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.14.6 References

d'Andrimont, R., Verhegghen, A., Lemoine, G., Kempeneers, P., Meroni, M., Van Der Velde, M., 2021. From parcel to continental scale—A first European crop type map based on Sentinel-1 and LUCAS Copernicus in-situ observations. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 266, 112708.

Zhang, Y., Liang, S., Ma, H., He, T., Wang, Q., Li, B., Xu, J., Zhang, G., Liu, X., Xiong, C., 2023. Generation of global 1-km daily soil moisture product from 2000 to 2020 using ensemble learning. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data Discuss.* 2023, 1–37.

1.15 SERENA T3.2 - Map of compaction projected under climate (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios) and land use change for Czechia

1.15.1 Data summary

The present dataset corresponds to one map of compaction projected under climate (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios) and land use change for Czechia. The maps are the result of applying the methods described in the Deliverable D5.1 (Coblinski *et al.*, 2023). We selected these two contrasting scenarios in order to explore different futures for national development of Czechia and their implications for climate and land use change over bulk density. The indicator selected was bulk density, and the soil threat was defined as "change over time in topsoil bulk density" as stated in Deliverable D5.1.

We employed digital soil mapping to project the bulk density, based on Quantile Regression Forest (QRF) algorithm. The algorithm was fitted with the covariates for the present, and the model was used to predict under land use and climate change scenarios by 2050.

The cross-validation shows that the model has an excellent performance with R^2 of 0.88 and RMSE of 0.04.

The most important variable used for predicting bulk density was clay content. Other important variables are elevation, land use and climate. Soil organic carbon content does not appear to have significant influence in bulk density. The prediction of bulk density for 2022 indicates that the change will be associated to clay.

SERENA had, among others, the objective of developing methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats and their bundles.

For this purpose, the maps in the present geodatasets were determined from

Table 1. Environmental-based covariates used in the predictive model using DSM approach for the assessment of soil compaction.

SCORPAN variables	Covariates	Unit	Spatial raw resolution	Source	
Soil	Bulk density	kg/dm ³	20 m	Research institute of soil and water conservation, Prague Czechia	Daniel Žížala zizala.daniel@vumop.cz
	Clay	%	20 m		
	Sand	%	20 m		
	Silt	%	20 m		
	Organic carbon content	%	20 m		
Topography	Aspect	no unit	50 m	Geoportal CUZK	https://geoportal.cuzk.cz/(S0zr1soc4f13vfjqtmak0v4n))/Default.aspx?lng=EN&mode=TextMeta&side=vyskopis&metadataID=CZ-CUZK-DMR4G-V&mapid=8&menu=301
	Elevation	m	50 m		
	Slope	%	50 m		

Climate	Bioclimatic variables*		1 km	See table 1	
		-			
Land use	Land use classes	no unit		See table 1	

Table 2. List of variables used to represent climate and land use changes scenarios used to assess soil compaction and the respective source. Climate data used for 2050 were the mean of the results produced by the two ACCESS-CM2 and HadGEM3-GC31-LL global climate models for the two selected SSPs (D5.1, Coblinski *et al.*, 2023)

Parameters	Variables	Unit	Raw resolution	Database	Period
Precipitation	Monthly total precipitation	mm			
Bioclimatic variables	Annual mean temperature	°C	1 km		Historical (1970-2000) to 2050 (SSP 1.2-6 and SSP 5.8-5)
	Mean Diurnal Range	°C			
	Isothermality	No unit			
	Temperature Seasonality	°C			
	Max Temperature of Warmest Month	°C			
	Min Temperature of Coldest Month	°C			
	Temperature Annual Range	°C			
	Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter	°C			
	Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter	°C		<i>worldclim.org</i> (Dix <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Good, 2019)	
	Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter	°C			
	Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter	°C			
	Annual Precipitation	mm			
	Precipitation of Wettest Month	mm			
	Precipitation of Driest Month	mm			
	Precipitation Seasonality	Fraction			

	Precipitation of Wettest Quarter	mm			
	Precipitation of Driest Quarter	mm			
	Precipitation of Warmest Quarter	mm			
	Precipitation of Coldest Quarter	mm			
Land use	Land use classes	No unit	100 m	<i>LUISA - joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/luisa_en</i> (Joint Research Centre, 2017)	2012 to 2050

The compaction maps for Czechia are 2.79 Mb

Although the dataset needs further validation, it is useful as a research tool to investigate soil compaction quantification under different land use and climate change scenarios for the SERENA consortium and other researchers.

1.15.2 FAIR data

1.15.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The geodatasets (geopackage files: SERENA_EJPSOIL_CZ_Compaction_ssp1.tif and SERENA_EJPSOIL_CZ_Compaction_ssp5.tif) will be made available in the general science repository Zenodo which will provide a DOI identifier. The name of the datasets follows the convention agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (e.g. SERENA_EJPSOIL_CZ_Compaction_ssp1). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include specific tags of the dataset: "soil threats", "SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios", "land use change", "compaction", "Czechia". The dataset correspond to single versions since there are no upgradable versions to the datasets in mind.

The project information will be also indicated in the metadata of the dataset: SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema and is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version

1.15.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset will be uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP-Soil community https://zenodo.org/communities/ejp_soil_research/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest. It will comply with the Zenodo's platform, and it will follow the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data will be made open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload, yet a 6-months period of embargo will apply in view of potential publications.

1.15.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a GeoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in ecosystem services bundles research.

1.15.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence will be the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licences/by/4.0/>). The data comes from applying the SERENA bundles cookbook. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.15.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.15.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.15.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.15.6 References

- Coblinski, J., Cornu, S., Saby, N. (2023). Deliverable D5.1 Maps of soil threat bundles by 2050.
- Žížala, D., Minařík, R., Skála, J., Beitlerová, H., Juřicová, A., Rojas, J. R., ... & Zádorová, T. (2022). High-resolution agriculture soil property maps from digital soil mapping methods, Czech Republic. *Catena*, 212, 106024.

1.16 SERENA T3.2 - Net Ecosystem Productivity of Peipsiääre municipality, Estonia

1.16.1 Data summary

Net Ecosystem Productivity (NEP) is an essential measure that reflects the balance between gross primary productivity and total ecosystem respiration. Evaluating NEP is crucial for understanding carbon dynamics, assessing ecosystem health, and determining their role in climate regulation.

The data gathered for the SERENA GHG Cookbook application serves the current NEP analysis. This analysis incorporated a range of datasets, including gross primary productivity (GPP) data from the 2014 MODIS dataset accessed through MODISTools in R, as well as daily soil moisture data from Zhang *et al.* (2023). Climate data, comprising maximum and minimum monthly temperatures for 2014, were sourced from World Climate datasets. Additionally, cropland data filtered for wheat from 2018 was derived from Sentinel-1 and LUCAS observations. The municipality's boundaries were acquired as vector data from the Republic of Estonia Land Board's Geoportal.

This study evaluated NEP in the Peipsiääre municipality under North European pedo-climatic conditions during the active growing season.

Two files were created: *SERENA_EJPSOIL_EE_GHG_Cookbook_NEP_May_wheat_yield* and *SERENA_EJPSOIL_EE_GHG_Cookbook_NEP_April8days_wheat_yields*, both formatted in GPKG, which facilitates efficient storage of geographic information and compatibility with various GIS applications. The data layers have sizes of 6.27 MB and will be valuable to the scientific community, particularly for NEP modeling efforts.

1.16.2 FAIR data

1.16.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

Within the SERENA project, the discoverability of data is ensured through the EJP SOIL guidelines and the strategic direction of project partners, which make datasets easily accessible and comprehensible for future research and applications. This approach is also reflected in the production of articles adhering to the same guiding principles.

The naming conventions for the files are designed to ensure clarity and consistency in data identification by incorporating descriptive elements that specify the geographic region (EE), the context (GHG Cookbook), and the specific data type (e.g., wheat yields), while also adhering to the convention established within SERENA's WP3 (Project_country_soilecosystemservice_indicator) to maintain consistency and traceability. The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words, linking the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number, and specific tags such as Estonia, Net Ecosystem Productivity (NEP), GHG, and Cookbook.

The metadata schema will be structured according to the QGIS schema and will be part of the dataset's file properties. It will include fields such as Title, Type, Language, Abstract, Keywords, Licences, Geographic information (layer CRS, extent, etc.), and Contact information.

The strategy for clear versioning involves implementing a version control system to monitor potential changes.

1.16.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

All generated data files were uploaded to Zenodo within the EJP-Soil-Serena community (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13959777>) and are openly accessible upon publication. A two-year embargo period will be applied to allow for potential publications. Users can access the data using free software tools like QGIS, which is available at QGIS.org, and further information can be found on the website. The data is stored in GPKG format, which is compatible with various software applications, ensuring broad usability. There are no privacy or data protection issues, as the dataset does not contain personal or sensitive information. Additionally, there are no contractual limitations, as the data has not been sourced from third parties or collaborators.

1.16.2.3 Making data interoperable:

The implementation of FAIR data principles ensures that data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. By adhering to these principles, data management practices are enhanced, facilitating better data sharing and collaboration among researchers. This approach will facilitate compliance with established formats and promote compatibility with various open software applications, enabling the recombination of our datasets with others from diverse origins.

1.16.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The data generated from the Net Ecosystem Productivity assessments are licenced under the Creative Commons Attribution Licence (CC BY 4.0; <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The data incorporates GHG Cookbook information, with quality assurance processes that include stakeholder evaluations to maintain the integrity and reliability of the findings. However, for enhanced accuracy in future assessments, it is important to consider relevant contextual factors and ensure that the data is validated to align with local conditions. The data will remain reusable in accordance with standard scientific practices.

1.16.3 Allocation of resources

The allocation of resources for ensuring the FAIR principles of data focuses on necessary processes and practices, utilizing a free access repository for data sharing. Data management is described in the established Data Management Plan (DMP) of the SERENA project.

1.16.4 Data security

The selected repository ensures that the data is securely stored in certified repositories for long-term preservation and management.

1.16.5 Ethical aspects

There are no personal data involved in the ethics review, the ethics section of the Description of Action (DoA), and the associated ethics deliverables, resulting in no ethical or legal issues affecting data sharing or informed consent for long-term preservation.

1.16.6 Other

No additional national, funder, sectorial, or departmental procedures for data management are being followed beyond the existing guidelines.

1.17 SERENA T3.2 - Impacts of Climate Change Scenarios on Net Ecosystem Productivity in Peipsiääre Municipality, Estonia

1.17.1 Data summary

Net Ecosystem Productivity (NEP), representing the balance between gross primary productivity and total ecosystem respiration, serves as an important measure for understanding carbon dynamics and assessing ecosystem health. When analysed in the context of varying greenhouse gas (GHG) scenarios, NEP assessments provide insights into potential future shifts in ecosystem functioning under changing climatic conditions. This approach facilitates the development of targeted strategies for enhancing carbon sequestration, mitigating GHG emissions, and strengthening ecosystem resilience under changing environmental conditions.

The data collected for the SERENA GHG Cookbook application supports the current analysis of Net Ecosystem Productivity (NEP) within different climate change scenarios. The analysis employed the GHG Cookbook methodology, utilizing various datasets, including gross primary productivity (GPP) from the 2014 MODIS dataset accessed via MODISTools in R, daily soil moisture data from Zhang *et al.* (2023), and climate data on maximum and minimum monthly temperatures for 2014 from World Climate datasets. Additionally, cropland data filtered for wheat from 2018 was derived from Sentinel-1 and LUCAS observations, while municipality boundaries were obtained as vector data from the Republic of Estonia Land Board's Geoportal.

Temperature and soil moisture projections under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios were made using data from Luhamaa *et al.* (2014) and the Climate Information Data Access Platform, which employed regional downscaling of global climate projections from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5 (CMIP5).

This study evaluates NEP across these climate change scenarios over an 8-day period in Peipsiääre municipality to assess the soil ecosystem service of greenhouse gas regulation and climate mitigation under varying GHG concentration pathways.

Two files were created: `SERENA_EJPSOIL_EE_CC_scenario_NEP_RCP4.5_2071-2100.gpkg` and `SERENA_EJPSOIL_EE_CC_scenario_NEP_RCP4.5_2041-2070.gpkg`, both formatted in GPKG, which facilitates efficient storage of geographic information and compatibility with various GIS applications.

1.17.2 FAIR data

1.17.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

Within the SERENA project, the discoverability of data is ensured through the EJP SOIL guidelines and the strategic direction of project partners, which make datasets easily accessible and comprehensible for future research and applications. This approach is also reflected in the production of articles adhering to the same guiding principles.

The naming conventions for the files are designed to ensure clarity and consistency in data identification by incorporating descriptive elements that specify the geographic region (EE), the context (CC scenario), the relevant climate scenario (RCP4.5), and the time period (e.g., 2071-2100 or 2041-2070), while also adhering to the convention established within SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilecosystemservice_indicator) to maintain consistency and traceability.

1.17.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The study provides valuable preliminary insights into NEP modelling; however, additional advanced analyses are necessary to refine the methodology and validate the data to address Estonia's specific pedoclimatic conditions. All generated datasets are made openly accessible through an open-access repository Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14000511>), following thorough analysis and subsequent publication. Users will be able to access the data using open-source tools such as QGIS, available at QGIS.org. The data will be stored in GPKG format, ensuring compatibility with a wide range of software applications and promoting broad usability. Data management will be conducted on unrestricted platforms to prevent technical barriers. Moreover, as the dataset does not include personal or sensitive information, there are no privacy or data protection concerns. There are no contractual limitations, as all data was independently produced and not sourced from third parties or collaborators.

1.17.2.3 Making data interoperable:

The implementation of FAIR data principles ensures that data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. By adhering to these principles, data management practices are enhanced, facilitating better data sharing and collaboration among researchers. This approach will facilitate compliance with established formats and promote compatibility with various open software applications, enabling the recombination of our datasets with others from diverse origins.

1.17.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The data generated from climate change scenarios evaluating the impact on Net Ecosystem Productivity will be licenced under the Creative Commons Attribution Licence (CC BY 4.0; <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>) following advanced analysis. Upon publication, there is no requirement for a data embargo, enabling immediate access for further research. However, for enhanced accuracy, it is important to consider relevant contextual factors and ensure that the data is validated to align with local conditions. The data will remain reusable in accordance with standard scientific practices.

1.17.3 Allocation of resources

The allocation of resources to ensure compliance with the FAIR data principles prioritizes implementing essential processes and practices, utilizing an open-access repository for data

dissemination upon completion and further refinement of the work prior to publication. Data management practices are outlined in the established Data Management Plan (DMP) of the SERENA project.

1.17.4 Data security

The selected repository ensures that the data is securely stored in certified repositories for long-term preservation and management.

1.17.5 Ethical aspects

There is no personal data involved in the ethics review, the ethics section of the Description of Action (DoA), and the associated ethics deliverables, resulting in no ethical or legal issues affecting data sharing or informed consent for long-term preservation.

1.17.6 Other

No additional national, funder, sectorial, or departmental procedures for data management are being followed beyond the existing guidelines.

1.18 SERENA T3.4 - Maps of Soil Organic Carbon Loss Scenarios in Elva Parish, Estonia

1.18.1 Data summary

Soil organic carbon (SOC) has a significant role in maintaining soil health and fertility, influencing agricultural productivity and environmental sustainability. Understanding the impact of different land management scenarios is essential for optimizing SOC levels and enhancing soil ecosystem services.

The analysis used a Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) stock map layer for Estonian mineral arable land soils, developed by the Centre of Estonian Rural Research and Knowledge. Projections of Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) stocks for two contrasting land management scenarios—bare soil during the winter months and continuous vegetation—were conducted using the RothC model, which simulates soil carbon turnover, over the period from 2020 to 2040. The average C inputs were calculated based on crop yield data and the amount of manure produced by livestock in Elva Parish during the period 2015–2020.

This study evaluated the effects of winter cropping systems on long-term soil fertility and their potential to mitigate SOC loss compared to bare soil conditions during the winter months.

Four files were created, all formatted in GPKG, which facilitates efficient storage of geographic information and compatibility with various GIS applications.

1.18.2 FAIR data

1.18.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

Within the SERENA project, the discoverability of data is ensured through the EJP SOIL guidelines and the strategic direction of project partners, which make datasets easily accessible and comprehensible for future research and applications.

The datasets (GeoPackage files: “SERENA_EJPSOIL_EE_SOClossscen_SOC_2040_Scenario1.gpkg, SERENA_EJPSOIL_EE_SOClossscen_SOC_2040_Scenario2.gpkg, SERENA_EJPSOIL_EE_SOClossscen_SOC_change_Scenario1.gpkg, SERENA_EJPSOIL_EE_SOClossscen_SOC_change_Scenario2.gpkg”) are published in the open-access repository Zenodo, which assigns a unique DOI identifier for citation and reference (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13991191>). The dataset naming follows the convention established within SERENA’s WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator) to ensure consistency and traceability. The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words in Zenodo, linking the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number, and specific metadata tags such as SOCloss, SOC, RothC, model, management, scenario and Estonia. Currently, the dataset is intended as a single version, with no subsequent updates or revisions planned.

The project information will be also indicated in the metadata of the dataset: SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema, and is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact

1.18.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

All created data files were uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP-Soil Serena community. A one-year embargo period will be applied to allow for potential publications. The dataset is provided in an open-source, platform-independent GeoPackage format, which is compatible with a wide range of GIS applications, including open-source software such as QGIS and proprietary systems like ArcGIS.

1.18.2.3 Making data interoperable:

The dataset is available in Geopackage format, accompanied by comprehensive metadata documentation. The implementation of FAIR data principles ensures that data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. By adhering to these principles, data management practices are enhanced, facilitating better data sharing and collaboration among researchers. This approach will facilitate compliance with established formats and promote compatibility with various open software applications, enabling the recombination of our datasets with others from diverse origins.

1.18.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The data generated from land management scenarios evaluating the impact on soil organic carbon (SOC) loss will be licenced under the Creative Commons Attribution Licence (CC BY 4.0; <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The data will remain reusable in accordance with standard scientific practices.

1.18.3 Allocation of resources

The allocation of resources for ensuring the FAIR principles of data focuses on necessary processes and practices, utilizing a free access repository for data sharing. Data management is described in the established Data Management Plan (DMP) of the SERENA project.

1.18.4 Data security

The selected repository ensures that the data is securely stored in certified repositories for long-term preservation and management.

1.18.5 Ethical aspects

There are no personal data involved in the ethics review, the ethics section of the Description of Action (DoA), and the associated ethics deliverables, resulting in no ethical or legal issues affecting data sharing or informed consent for long-term preservation.

1.18.6 Other

No additional national, funder, sectorial, or departmental procedures for data management are being followed beyond the existing guidelines.

1.19 SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil organic carbon loss of mineral soils in Estonia

1.19.1 Data summary

The map was generated for the purpose to evaluate soil organic carbon (SOC) loss in Estonian agricultural soils. It is directly related to SERENA project WP3, T3.2, D3.3 with the aim of applying cookbooks to assess soil threats or ecosystem services. This map is the outcome of applying a cookbook developed by ISRIC (Genova, G., Poggio, L., Kempen, B., & Colman, B. DSM Workflow Seedling. ISRIC - World Soil Information. <https://doi.org/10.17027/ISRIC-FSX2-2691>) to evaluate the soil threat SOC loss.

The generated map of SOC loss expressed as absolute sequestration rate between 2015 and 2021 is in GEOTIFF format at the resolution of 100m in the reference system WGS84. The input data for the cookbook was from the PANDA database, which contains regular soil monitoring and voluntary soil sampling data by farmers in Estonia. The database contains soil sampling data collected from agricultural lands for the period 2015–2021 and is managed by the Centre of Estonian Rural Research and Knowledge. To achieve the aim for accounting SOC loss in agricultural soils, re-visited locations were used to calculate the change in SOC stock. The selection of temporal pairs of PANDA data resulted

with 1037 paired points where the interval between second sampling was more than 5 years. SOC was analyzed with the wet oxidation method (sulfochromic oxidation, similar to Walkley-Black). The covariates in the EU scale were used (except for land use covariates): The list with the URLs can be found here. The size of the map is 4,73 MB.

1.19.2 FAIR data

1.19.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geoTIFF file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_EE_SOCLOSS_COOKBOOK.tif") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13986639>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "SOCLOSS", "SOC", "Geostatistics", "ESTONIA", "MINERAL SOIL". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema in .docx format, and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.19.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP-Soil Serena community. It complies with Zenodo's platform, and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geoTIFF) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data are open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload, yet a 6-months period of embargo will apply in view of potential publications.

1.19.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in ecosystem services bundles research.

1.19.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The data comes from applying the SERENA bundles cookbook. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.19.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated long-term.

1.19.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.19.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.20 SERENA T3.2 - Map of SESs/STs Bundles for Estonian agricultural land

1.20.1 Data summary

The map was generated for the purpose to evaluate bundles of SES/ST in Estonian agricultural soils. It is directly related to SERENA project WP3, T3.2, D3.3 with the aim of applying cookbooks to assess the bundles of available soil threats or soil ecosystem services. This map is the outcome of applying a bundles cookbook developed in SERENA based on soil threats SOC loss and erosion potential and SES biomass production. The resulting bundles are clusters of SESs/STs where the intra-cluster variability is lower than the inter-cluster variability in the mean values of the selected SESs/STs to identify the bundles.

The generated map of SESs/STs Bundles for Estonian agricultural land is in GEOTIFF format at the resolution of 100m in the reference system WGS84. The input data for the cookbook was the Map of soil organic carbon loss of mineral soils in Estonia described in section 1.2; Soil water erosion potential in agricultural soils modelled by USLE, and primary biomass production as described in section 'Map of SESs/STs Bundles for Europe (EU)'. The size of the map is 1,20 MB.

1.20.2 FAIR data

1.20.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geoTIFF file:"SERENA_EJP SOIL_EE_BUNDLES_COOKBOOK.tif") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951146>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the

dataset: “SERENA” “EJP-SOIL”, “SOCLOSS”, “BUNDLES”, “EROSION”, “BIOMASS”, “ESTONIA”, “MINERAL SOIL”. The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema in .docx format, and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.20.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP-Soil Serena community. It complies with Zenodo's platform, and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geoTIFF) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data are open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload, yet a 6-months period of embargo will apply in view of potential publications.

1.20.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in ecosystem services bundles research.

1.20.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The data comes from applying the SERENA bundles cookbook. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.20.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated long-term.

1.20.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.20.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.21 SERENA T3.2 - Erosion control map of Hungary

1.21.1 Data summary

The present data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil erosion and soil erosion control cookbook for the territory of Hungary. The map of soil loss by water erosion (soil threat) was based on the RUSLE model. For the soil erosion control, the difference between the erosion map without vegetation (C-factor = 1) and the erosion map with vegetation was calculated. The erosion maps with-, and without vegetation were categorized according to the cookbook, and the result map shows how many categories the pixel has changed when vegetation is taken into account.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil loss was used as an indicator for soil erosion (ST).

To create the soil loss map we used data on yearly precipitation of CARPATCLIM database, and AGRI4CAST MARS (R-factor); sand-, silt-, and clay content of DOSoReMI.hu database, and SOC map compiled in the framework of SERENA (K-factor); ESDAC LS-factor for the EU; ESDAC Cover Management factor for the EU (C-factor); ESDAC Support Practices factor for the EU (P-factor).

The delivered map was prepared in GeoTIFF format in the resolution of 100 * 100 m.

1.21.2 FAIR data

1.21.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geopackage file: "SERENA_EJP_SOIL_HU_EROSION_erosioncontrol.gpkg") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006182>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilecosystemservice_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "erosion control", "water erosion", "RUSLE", "Hungary". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema will be created and includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords

- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.21.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.21.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geopackage file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil erosion by water modelling.

1.21.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA Erosion and Erosion Control cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Hungary. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.21.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.21.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.21.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.22 SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil loss by water erosion of Hungary

1.22.1 Data summary

The present data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil erosion and soil erosion control cookbook for the territory of Hungary. The map of soil loss by water erosion (soil threat) was based on the RUSLE model.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil loss was used as an indicator for soil erosion (ST).

To create the soil loss map we used data on yearly precipitation of CARPATCLIM database, and AGRI4CAST MARS (R-factor); sand-, silt-, and clay content of DOSoReMI.hu database, and SOC map compiled in the framework of SERENA (K-factor); ESDAC LS-factor for the EU; ESDAC Cover Management factor for the EU (C-factor); ESDAC Support Practices factor for the EU (P-factor).

The delivered map was prepared in GeoTIFF format in the resolution of 100 * 100 m.

1.22.2 FAIR data

1.22.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geopackage file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_HU_EROSION_soilerosion.gpkg") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006018>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "erosion", "water erosion", "RUSLE", "Hungary". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema will be created and includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.22.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.22.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geopackage file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil erosion by water modelling.

1.22.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA Erosion and Erosion Control cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Hungary. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.22.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.22.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.22.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.23 SERENA T3.2 - Soil organic carbon concentration map for the topsoil of Hungary

1.23.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA SOC loss cookbook for the territory of Hungary.

Random forest kriging (RFK, combination of the random forest machine learning algorithm and the kriging technique) was used for the prediction of the SOC concentration.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats (ST). Soil organic carbon concentration was used as an indicator for soil organic carbon loss (ST).

To compile the soil organic carbon map, we used soil organic carbon (0-30 cm, year 2016) data of the Hungarian Soil Information and Monitoring System (SIMS), which are not publicly available.

The selection of environmental covariates, which are then used to model and map SOC content, was based on the 'scorpan' model: (s) soil properties, (c) climate, (o) organisms, (r) relief, (p) parent material, (a) age and (n) spatial coordinates. The following covariates were used: soil type map of Hungary (Pásztor *et al.*, 2018); long-term mean annual evapotranspiration, -evaporation, -precipitation, and -temperature (Szentimrey *et al.*, 2007); CORINE Land Cover 2012; EU-DEM and derivatives; Geological map of Hungary (Gyalog & Síkhegyi, 2005).

Delivered map was prepared in GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 100 * 100 m.

1.23.2 FAIR data

1.23.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geopackage file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_HU_SOCLOSS_SOC.gpkg") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14002688>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "SOCLOSS", "SOC", "digital soil mapping", "HUNGARY". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema will be created and includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.23.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.23.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geopackage file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil organic carbon modelling.

1.23.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA SOC loss cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Hungary. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.23.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.23.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.23.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.24 SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil loss by water erosion of the Ireland

1.24.1 Data summary

The present data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil erosion and soil erosion control cookbook (Buttafuoco *et al.*, 2024). The RUSLE (Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation) was calculated following the cookbook methodology. The RUSLE equation, $R * K * LS * C * P$, incorporates the factors representing rainfall erosivity (R), soil erodibility (K), topographic factor (LS), cover management (C), and support practice (P). The resulting values indicate the potential average annual soil loss in tons per hectare per year.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil loss was used as an indicator for the soil threat soil erosion.

The methods and data used to create the soil loss map are described in Buttafuoco *et al.* (2024) and Hessel *et al.* (2024).

1.24.2 FAIR data

1.24.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geopackage file: "SERENA_EJP_SOIL_IE_EROSION_SOILLOSS.gpkg") is available in the EJP Soil-Serena community in the Zenodo repository; and is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13987789>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilecosystemservice_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "erosion", "water erosion", "RUSLE", "IRELAND". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema in .docx format, and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.24.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP Soil community and will be Open Access. It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the SERENA project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.24.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geopackage file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms.

1.24.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA Erosion and Erosion Control cookbook (Buttafuoco *et al.*, 2024) applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for the Netherlands. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.24.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated in the long-term.

1.24.4 Data security

Data security is provided by Zenodo.

1.24.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues.

1.24.6 References

Buttafuoco *et al.*, 2024. Cookbook to evaluate indicators of soil threats, soil-based ES and their associated bundles over scenarios of change. SERENA deliverable 2.3.2 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13993620>

Hessel R, G Buttafuoco, E Medina-Roldán, D Smiraglia, J Coblinski, L Kuk, B Lemercier, S Pindral, J Reyes Rojas, R Lorenzetti, C Pesch, K Amalevičiūtė-Volungė, S Asins, F Assennato, A Astover, Z Bakacsi, A Benó, G Bondi, T Brunner, S Callewaert, K Cockx, J Cruijisen, P Csontos, E Doñate, A Fahy, V Feiza, C B Foldal, A Gaillot, L Gardin, C Gedeon, D Josipovic, P Kassai, T Kikas, M Kocsis, A Laborczi, D Luts, J Makovníková, D Montagne, K Oorts, L O'Sullivan, B Pálka, L Pásztor, E Putku, N Riitano, N Saby, E Schmaltz, V Shahrokh, B Szabó, G Szatmári, M Trip, F Ungaro, J Volungevičius, T Weninger, R Žydelis. 2024. Assessment of Soil Threats and Ecosystem Services from each MS with the harmonized procedures. SERENA deliverable 3.3, 224 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13991087>

1.25 SERENA T3.2 - Map of Net Ecosystem Productivity for county level assessment in Ireland

1.25.1 Data summary

An 8-day NEP analysis was conducted for the entirety of the Republic of Ireland under wheat crop from 02-09 of January. However, wheat production in Ireland is largely centred around several key regions in the east/central-east due to the relative dominance of grassland and alternative agricultural regimes elsewhere, therefore County Meath was selected. Nine MODIS tiles to cover the extent of Ireland were merged and exported to QGIS for analysis.

SERENA had, among others, the objective of developing methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. NEP was used as an indicator of greenhouse gases and climate regulation supported by soils.

Although the dataset needs further validation, it is useful as a research tool to investigate CO₂ fluxes in the region for the SERENA consortium and other researchers.

1.25.2 FAIR data

1.25.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geoTIFF file: “SERENA_EJPSOIL_NL_GHG_IE.tif”) is available in the general science repository Zenodo which will provide a DOI identifier. The name of the dataset follows the convention agreed upon in SERENA’s WP3 (project_country_soilecosystemservice_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include specific tags of the dataset: “greenhouse gases and climate regulation indicators”, “net ecosystem productivity”, “IRELAND”. The dataset consists in a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset in mind.

The project information will be also indicated in the metadata of the dataset: SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema, and is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version

1.25.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP Soil Serena community. It is Open Access.

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.25.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geopackage file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in carbon fluxes research.

1.25.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The data comes from applying the SERENA GHG

cookbook which applied different filters to eliminate NEP values inconsistencies. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.25.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.25.4 Data security

Data security is provided by Zenodo.

1.25.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research and is spatially aggregated.

1.26 SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil organic carbon of Ireland

1.26.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA SOC loss cookbook. For Ireland, the application was carried out at national scale.

A map of SOC concentrations for the Republic of Ireland was produced using a geostatistical approach. Particularly, ordinary kriging (Chilès & Delfiner, 2012) was used to map SOC concentration (%) at national scale.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil organic carbon concentration was used as an indicator for soil organic carbon loss (ST).

No direct comparison was possible because there was no previous SOC map. The Indicative Soil Organic Carbon Stock Map of Irish Agricultural Soils (0-50cm) by Creamer *et al.* (2016) offers an indicative comparison, although it is not directly comparable.

Delivered data was validated by stakeholders from Ireland (multi-stakeholders) in September, 2024.

1.26.2 FAIR data

1.26.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geoTIFF file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_IE_SOCLOSS_SOC.tif") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13970637>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the

dataset: “SERENA” “EJP-SOIL”, “SOCLOSS”, “SOC”, “Geostatistics”, “IRELAND”. The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.26.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP-Soil Serena community. It complies with the Zenodo’s platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data are open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload, yet a 6-months period of embargo will apply in view of potential publications.

1.26.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geopackage file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil organic carbon modelling.

1.26.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA SOC loss cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Ireland. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.26.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.26.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.26.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.27 SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil sealing of Ireland

1.27.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil Sealing cookbook. For Ireland, the application was carried out at county scale for Co. Wexford. The study area, County Wexford, is a significant agricultural hub located in the Southeast of Ireland.

The map of soil sealing (soil threat) was based on classification of multitemporal satellite images and photointerpretation. The methodology uses vegetation and backscatter indices calculated over time series of images, and decision rules. The semi-automatic classification supports the subsequent photointerpretation phase based on national orthophotos and other free VHR satellite images (e.g. through Google Earth or Bing services). The final maps are the product of a binary classification (sealed/not-sealed) having 10 m spatial resolution

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. The selected indicator was degree of soil sealing. By evaluating this degree at two moments in time, the change in soil sealing can be determined.

To create the soil sealing map, we used Sentinel-1 C-band synthetic aperture radar imaging and Sentinel-2 Multispectral Instrument (MSI) (<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>) for the semi-automatic classification, and Google Earth images for the photointerpretation.

Delivered map was prepared in the GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 10 m.

Delivered data was validated by stakeholders from Ireland (scientists and technicians) in September 2024.

1.27.2 FAIR data

1.27.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (GeoTIFF file: "SERENA_EJP_SOIL_SEALING_SEALINGDEGREE.TIF") will be available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it will be provided with a DOI identifier. The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-

SOIL”, “soil sealing”, “remote sensing”, “satellite images”, “photointerpretation”, “IRELAND”. The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema in .txt format, and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version

1.27.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset will be uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. It will comply with the Zenodo’s platform and it will follow the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (GeoTIFF) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.27.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a GeoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil sealing research.

1.27.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence will be the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA Soil Sealing cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Ireland. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.27.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.27.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.27.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.28 Map of SESs/STs Bundles for Europe (EU)

1.28.1 Data summary

The present dataset corresponds to 4 maps of soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats for the area of the EU. The maps are the result of applying the bundles cookbook developed in SERENA/EJP-Soil to the area of interest (AOI) input data. The resulting bundles are clusters of SESs/STs where the intra-cluster variability is lower than the inter-cluster variability in the mean values of the selected SESs/STs to identify the bundles.

SERENA had, among others, the objective of developing methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats and their bundles.

For this purpose, the bundles in the present geodatasets were determined from 3 spatially-explicit datasets to which the bundles cookbook was applied within the AOI: (1) eroded soil organic carbon (ESDAC Pan-European SOC stock of agricultural soils dataset, published in Lugato *et al.* 2016), (2) biomass production (ESDAC Soil Biomass Productivity maps of grasslands and pasture, of croplands and of forest areas in the European Union dataset, published in Tóth *et al.* (2013), and (3) water erosion (ESDAC Multiple concurrent soil erosion processes dataset, published in Borrelli *et al.* (2022).

The 4 geodatasets of bundles are in vector format and are:

Bundles' geodataset name	Description	Size
SERENA_EJPSoil_Bundles_cookbook_EUmap1.gpkg	Bundle map in which the input geodata was not filled for spatial gaps, variables are min-max-scaled and the extent is the EU	201.2 Mb
SERENA_EJPSoil_Bundles_cookbook_EUmap2.gpkg	Bundle map in which the input geodata was not filled for spatial gaps, variables are min-max-scaled and the extent is the Mediterranean climatic zone of the EU	
SERENA_EJPSoil_Bundles_cookbook_EUmap3.gpkg	Bundle map in which the input geodata was filled for spatial gaps, variables are	382.2 Mb

	min-max-scaled and the extent is the EU	
SERENA_EJPSoil_Bundles_cookbook_EUmap4.gpkg	Bundle map in which the input geodata was filled for spatial gaps, variables are not min-max-scaled and the extent is the EU	382.2 Mb

Although the dataset needs further validation, it is useful as a research tool to investigate co-occurrence of SESs and STs for the SERENA consortium and other researchers.

1.28.2 FAIR data

1.28.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The geodatasets (geopackage files: see names above) are available in the general science repository Zenodo which provides a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14002135> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14002270> for R code). The name of the datasets follows the convention agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilecosystemservice_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include specific tags of the dataset: "soil-based ecosystem services co-occurrence", "soil threats co-occurrence", "soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats bundles", "European Union". The dataset correspond to single versions since there are no upgradable versions to the datasets in mind.

The project information will be also indicated in the metadata of the dataset: SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema, and is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version

1.28.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP-Soil Serena community. It complies with the Zenodo's platform, and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data are open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload, yet a 6-months period of embargo will apply in view of potential publications.

1.28.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geopackage file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in ecosystem services bundles research.

1.28.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licences/by/4.0/>). The data comes from applying the SERENA bundles cookbook. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.28.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.28.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.28.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.28.6 References

Borrelli, P., Panagos, P., Alewell, C., Ballabio, C., de Oliveira Fagundes, H., Haregeweyn, N., Lugato, E., Maerker, M., Poesen, J., Vanmaercke, M. and Robinson, D.A., 2022. Policy implications of multiple concurrent soil erosion processes in European farmland. *Nature Sustainability*. DOI: 10.1038/s41893-022-00988-4.

Lugato, E., Paustian, K., Panagos, P., Jones, A., Borrelli, P., 2016. Quantifying the erosion effect on current carbon budget of European agricultural soils at high spatial resolution. *Global Change Biology* (2016), 22(5), 1976–1984, doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13198>

Tóth, G., Gardi, C., Bódis, K., Ivits, É., Aksoy, E., Jones, A., Jeffrey, S., Petursdottir, T. and Montanarella, L., 2013. Continental-scale assessment of provisioning soil functions in Europe. *Ecological Processes*, 2, pp.1-18.

1.29 SERENA T3.2 - Map of Net Ecosystem Productivity of Emilia-Romagna Italy

1.29.1 Data summary

The present dataset corresponds to a map of Net Ecosystem Productivity (NEP) for areas of the Emilia-Romagna region in Italy classified as wheat by the Eurocrop 2028 spatial product (d'Andrimont *et al.* 2021). The map is the result of applying the NEP cookbook developed in SERENA/EJP-Soil to the area of interest (AOI) input data. NEP is expressed for a single 8-day period in early summer as it is the date with the highest value. The NEP value is a 2010-2014 average for the particular 8-day period. The data description document of the cookbook (hereafter "GHG cookbook") itself corresponds to another document of the SERENA project.

SERENA had, among others, the objective of developing methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. NEP was used as an indicator of greenhouse gases and climate regulation supported by soils.

For this purpose, NEP was calculated from (data origin) 4 spatially-explicit datasets to which the GHG cookbook was applied within the AOI: (1) maximum monthly air temperature from WorldClimate, (2) minimum monthly air temperature from WorldClimate, (3) MODIS MOD17A2HGF collection, and (4) daily soil moisture data derived from Zhang *et al.* (2023). (5) The Eurocrop 2018 database was used to filter the spatialisation of the indicator to wheat areas, and (6) the AOI border.

The NEP map for Emilia-Romagna in vector format is 199 Mb.

Although the dataset needs further validation, it is useful as a research tool to investigate CO₂ fluxes in the region for the SERENA consortium and other researchers.

1.29.2 FAIR data

1.29.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geopackage file: "SERENA_EJP_SOIL_IT_GHG_NEP.gpkg") is available in the general science repository Zenodo which provides a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951142>). The name of the dataset follows the convention agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilecosystemservice_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include specific tags of the dataset: "greenhouse gases and climate regulation indicators", "net ecosystem productivity", "Emilia-Romagna, Italy". The dataset consists in a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset in mind.

The project information will be also indicated in the metadata of the dataset: SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema, and is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.

- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version

1.29.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP-Soil Serena community. It complies with the Zenodo's platform, and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data are open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload, yet a 6-months period of embargo will apply in view of potential publications.

1.29.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geopackage file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in carbon fluxes research.

1.29.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licences/by/4.0/>). The data comes from applying the SERENA GHG cookbook which applied different filters to eliminate NEP values inconsistencies. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.29.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.29.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.29.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.29.6 References

d'Andrimont, R., Verhegghen, A., Lemoine, G., Kempeneers, P., Meroni, M., Van Der Velde, M., 2021. From parcel to continental scale—A first European crop type map based on Sentinel-1 and LUCAS Copernicus in-situ observations. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 266, 112708.

Zhang, Y., Liang, S., Ma, H., He, T., Wang, Q., Li, B., Xu, J., Zhang, G., Liu, X., Xiong, C., 2023. Generation of global 1-km daily soil moisture product from 2000 to 2020 using ensemble learning. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data Discuss.* 2023, 1–37.

1.30 SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil organic carbon of Tuscany (Italy)

1.30.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA SOC loss cookbook (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13993621>). For Italy, the application was carried out at regional scale in Tuscany Region (Italy).

The map of soil organic carbon (as an indicator of SOC loss threat) was based on ordinary kriging coupled with local geostatistics (LGS) approach.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil organic carbon concentration was used as an indicator for soil organic carbon loss (ST).

To create the soil organic carbon map, we used soil organic carbon (0-0.30 m) data of Tuscany Region database, which are not freely available (Lamma Consortium, info@lamma.toscana.it).

Delivered map was prepared in the GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 50 m.

Delivered data was validated by stakeholders from Italy (scientists) in September, 2024.

1.30.2 FAIR data

1.30.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geoTIFF file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_IT_SOCLOSS_SOC.tif") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951265>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "SOCLOSS", "SOC", "Geostatistics", "ITALY". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords

- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.30.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP Soil SERENA community (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951265>). It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geoTIFF) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data is made open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload.

1.30.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil organic carbon modelling.

1.30.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA SOC loss cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Tuscany Region (Italy). No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.30.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.30.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.30.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.31 SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil sealing of Italy

1.31.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil Sealing cookbook. For Italy, the application was carried out at national scale.

The map of soil sealing (soil threat) was based on classification of multitemporal satellite images and photointerpretation. The methodology uses vegetation and backscatter indices calculated over time series of images, and decision rules. The semi-automatic classification supports the subsequent photointerpretation phase based on national orthophotos and other free VHR satellite images (e.g. through Google Earth or Bing services). The final maps are the product of a binary classification (sealed/not-sealed) having 10 m spatial resolution

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. The selected indicator was degree of soil sealing. By evaluating this degree at two moments in time, the change in soil sealing can be determined.

To create the soil sealing map, we used Sentinel-1 C-band synthetic aperture radar imaging and Sentinel-2 Multispectral Instrument (MSI) (<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>) for the semi-automatic classification, and Google Earth images for the photointerpretation.

Delivered map was prepared in the GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 10 m.

Delivered data was validated by stakeholders from Italy (scientists and technicians) in September 2024.

1.31.2 FAIR data

1.31.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (GeoTIFF file: "SERENA_EJP_SOIL_IT_SOILSEALING_SEALINGDEGREE.TIF") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951144>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "soil sealing", "remote sensing", "satellite images", "photointerpretation", "ITALY". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema in .txt format, and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links
- History/version

1.31.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (GeoTIFF) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.31.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a GeoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil sealing research.

1.31.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA Soil Sealing cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Italy. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.31.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.31.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.31.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.31.6 Other

None.

1.32 SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil loss by water erosion of Tuscany (Italy)

1.32.1 Data summary

The present data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil erosion and soil erosion control cookbook. For Italy we selected the region Tuscany.

The map of soil loss by water erosion (soil threat) was based on the RUSLE model.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil loss was used as an indicator for soil erosion (ST).

To create the soil loss map we used: not freely available database of meteorological parameters spatialized at 250 m (minimum and maximum daily air temperature; cumulate daily precipitation) over Tuscany region (period 1990–2022, Lamma Consortium) and a local linear equation between R and mean annual precipitation (P) (R-factor), Regional Land use map 1:10.000 (2018, freely available at: <https://www502.regione.toscana.it/geoscopio/usocoperturasuolo.html>) and ESDAC method (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2015.05.021>) (C-factor); Sand, silt, clay, and OC (%) maps (built from 4.000 soil profiles, following FAO's methodology in GSP-GSOC map Lamma Consortium)), (K-factor, following Torri *et al.* (1997); Desmet and Govers (1996) SAGA tool was applied at 10 m and upscaled to 50m by bilinear interpolation (DEM 10 m of Tuscany, freely available at <https://www502.regione.toscana.it/geoscopio/cartoteca.html#99>) (LS-factor); and for P-factor, for terraced areas a multiplication factor of 0.5 was considered (expert evaluation) (Not freely available database 1:10.00 of terraced areas (2020), Lamma Consortium)..

Both delivered maps were prepared in the GeoTIFF format in the resolution of 100m.

Delivered data will be validated by stakeholders from Italy (scientist) in October, 2024.

1.32.2 FAIR data

1.32.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (single band raster file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_IT_Tuscany_erosion.tif", plus file of style: SERENA_EJPSOIL_IT_TUscany_erosion.qml) is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951151>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3. The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA project", "EJP-Soil", "soil threats", "Soil erosion", "RUSLE", "Italy", "Tuscany". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created in Zenodo, including the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Links (DOI from Zenodo)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.32.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (Geotiff) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

Also, a style file was shared;

The data are open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload, yet a 12-months period of embargo will apply in view of potential publications.

1.32.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a single band raster file. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil erosion by water modelling.

1.32.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The data comes from applying the SERENA Erosion and Erosion Control cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Tuscany. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.32.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this.

1.32.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.32.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.33 SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil mass not eroded of Tuscany (Italy)

1.33.1 Data summary

One of the objectives of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. The present data was prepared according to the methodology of the SERENA Soil erosion and soil erosion control cookbook. Soil loss was used as an indicator for soil erosion (ST). The map of soil mass not eroded was based on the RUSLE model. Soil erosion control was calculated as the difference between potential and actual soil erosion (SES, ecosystem service of soil erosion protection, i.e., soil eroded mass retained by vegetation, Mg/ha/y). For Italy, the cookbook was applied in the Tuscany region.

To create the soil loss map we used:

- for R-factor, not freely available database of meteorological parameters spatialized at 250 m (minimum and maximum daily air temperature; cumulate daily precipitation) over Tuscany region (period 1990–2022, Lamma Consortium) and a local linear equation between R and mean annual precipitation (P);
- for C -factor, Regional Land use map 1:10.000 (2018, freely available at: <https://www502.regione.toscana.it/geoscopio/usocoperturasuolo.html>) and ESDAC method (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2015.05.021>) ;
- for K-factor, sand, silt, clay, and O.C. (%) maps (built from 4.000 soil profiles, following FAO's methodology in GSP-GSOC map, Lamma Consortium), and Torri *et al.* (1997) function;
- for LS-factor, DEM 10 m of Tuscany, (freely available at <https://www502.regione.toscana.it/geoscopio/cartoteca.html99>) and Desmet & Govers (1996) SAGA tool (applied at 10 m and upscaled);
- for P-factor, not freely available database 1:10.00 of terraced areas (Lamma Consortium, 2020) (for terraced areas a multiplication factor of 0.5 was considered, based on expert evaluation)

Maps was delivered in the GeoTIFF format in the resolution of 100m.

Delivered data will be validated by stakeholders from Italy (scientist) in October, 2024.

1.33.2 FAIR data

1.33.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (single band raster file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_IT_TUscany_erosion_control.tif") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13952097>). The name of the data follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3. The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA project" "EJP-Soil", "soil erosion control", "RUSLE", "Italy", "Tuscany". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created in Zenodo , including the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Links (DOI from Zenodo)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.33.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (GeoTIFF) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.33.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a single band raster file in GeoTIFF. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil erosion control modelling.

1.33.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The data comes from applying the SERENA Erosion and Erosion Control cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Tuscany. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

The data are open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload, yet a 12-months period of embargo will apply in view of potential publications.

1.33.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this.

1.33.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.33.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.34 SERENA T3.2 - Maps of topsoil (0-30 cm) parameters of Tuscany (Italy)

1.34.1 Data summary

The objective of SERENA project was to develop and apply methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Some topsoil (0-30 cm) parameters were created in the frame of the project SERENA, to be used in the frame of cookbooks applications for Italy.

The data was prepared based on DSM approach at regional scale for Tuscany Region (Italy).

The map of soil organic carbon stock (t/ha), sand, clay, and silt content (%), rock fragments content (%), bulk density (g/cm³), pH were built on a 100 m grid and published in GeoTIFF format.

To create all parameter maps, we used about 4.000 soil profile data collected in Tuscany Region database, (not freely available, Lamma Consortium, info@lamma.toscana.it).

Delivered map was prepared in the GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 100 m.

1.34.2 FAIR data

1.34.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The datasets are available in the general science repository of Zenodo, in the SERENA community and they are provided under a unique DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14039385>). The name of the datasets follows the general conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3:

- soil organic carbon stock (t/ha): serena_ejpsoil_IT_TUS_Cstok30.tiff
- sand, clay, and silt content (%): serena_ejpsoil_IT_TUS_clay30.tiff; serena_ejpsoil_IT_TUS_sand.tiff; serena_ejpsoil_IT_TUS_silt.tiff
- rock fragments content (%): serena_ejpsoil_IT_TUS_RF30.tiff
- bulk density (g/cm³): serena_ejpsoil_IT_TUS_BD30.tiff
- pH: serena_ejpsoil_IT_TUS_pH30.tiff

The keywords used to make the datasets findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA project", "EJP-SOIL", "WP3", "ITALY", "Tuscany", "topsoil", "digital soil mapping", "carbon stock", "texture", "sand", "silt", "clay", "ph". The datasets consist of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

Metadata are reported in the description of the dataset file properties in Zenodo. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the datasets
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Links (when the information will add to Zenodo this will be used)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.34.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The datasets were uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP-Soil Serena community (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14039385>). It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The datasets use an open-source, platform-independent format (GeoTIFF) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data are open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload, yet a 12-months period of embargo will apply in view of potential publications.

1.34.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the datasets are provided as a geoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms.

1.34.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The datasets licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY) 4.0. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.34.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the datasets FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the datasets does not know how to estimate this.

1.34.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.34.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.35 SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil loss by water erosion of the Netherlands

1.35.1 Data summary

The present data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil erosion and soil erosion control cookbook (Buttafuoco *et al.*, 2024). The map of soil loss by water erosion (soil threat) was based on the RUSLE model.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil loss was used as an indicator for the soil threat soil erosion.

The methods and data used to create the soil loss map are described in Buttafuoco *et al.* (2024) and Hessel *et al.* (2024).

The soil loss map is provided as geopackage file and has resolution of 25 m.

1.35.2 FAIR data

1.35.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geopackage file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_NL_EROSION_SOILLOSS.gpkg") is available in the EJP Soil Serena community in the Zenodo repository, and is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951679>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilecosystemservice_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words

relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: “SERENA” “EJP-SOIL”, “erosion”, “water erosion”, “RUSLE”, “The Netherlands”. The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema in .docx format, and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.35.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP Soil Serena community and is Open Access (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951679>). It complies with the Zenodo’s platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the SERENA project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.35.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geopackage file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil erosion by water modelling.

1.35.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA Erosion and Erosion Control cookbook (Buttafuoco *et al.*, 2024) applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for the Netherlands. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.35.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated in the long-term.

1.35.4 Data security

Data security is provided by Zenodo.

1.35.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues. All data that have been used are openly available (see Hessel *et al.*, 2024) and are of aggregated nature.

1.35.6 References

Buttafuoco *et al.* 2024. Cookbook to evaluate indicators of soil threats, soil-based ES and their associated bundles over scenarios of change. SERENA deliverable 2.3.2. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13993620>

Hessel R, G Buttafuoco, E Medina-Roldán, D Smiraglia, J Coblinski, L Kukk, B Lemerrier, S Pindral, J Reyes Rojas, R Lorenzetti, C Pesch, K Amalevičiūtė-Volungė, S Asins, F Assennato, A Astover, Z Bakacsi, A Benó, G Bondi, T Brunner, S Callewaert, K Cockx, J Cruijisen, P Csontos, E Doñate, A Fahy, V Feiza, C B Foldal, A Gaillot, L Gardin, C Gedeon, D Josipovic, P Kassai, T Kikas, M Kocsis, A Laborczi, D Luts, J Makovniková, D Montagne, K Oorts, L O’Sullivan, B Pálka, L Pásztor, E Putku, N Riitano, N Saby, E Schmaltz, V Shahrokh, B Szabó, G Szatmári, M Trip, F Ungaro, J Volungevičius, T Weninger, R Žydelis. 2024. Assessment of Soil Threats and Ecosystem Services from each MS with the harmonized procedures. SERENA deliverable 3.3, 224 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13991087>

1.36 SERENA T3.2 - Map of Net Ecosystem Productivity of the Netherlands

1.36.1 Data summary

The present dataset corresponds to a map of Net Ecosystem Productivity (NEP) for areas in the Netherlands classified as wheat by the Eurocrop 2028 spatial product (d’Andrimont *et al.* 2021). The map is the result of applying the NEP cookbook developed (Buttafuoco *et al.*, 2024) in SERENA/EJP-Soil to the area of interest (AOI) input data. NEP is expressed for a single 8-day period in early summer as it is the date with the highest value. The NEP value is a 2010-2014 average for the particular 8-day period.

SERENA had, among others, the objective of developing methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. NEP was used as an indicator of greenhouse gases and climate regulation supported by soils.

For this purpose, NEP was calculated from (data origin) 4 spatially-explicit datasets to which the GHG cookbook was applied within the AOI: (1) maximum monthly air temperature from WorldClimate, (2) minimum monthly air temperature from WorldClimate, (3) MODIS MOD17A2HGF collection, and (4) daily soil moisture data derived from Zhang *et al.* (2023). (5) The Eurocrop 2018 database was used to filter the spatialisation of the indicator to wheat areas, and (6) the AOI border.

The NEP map for the Netherlands is 62 Mb and has pixel size of 500 m.

Although the dataset needs further validation, it is useful as a research tool to investigate CO₂ fluxes in the region for the SERENA consortium and other researchers.

1.36.2 FAIR data

1.36.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geoTIFF file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_NL_GHG_NEP.tif") is available in the general science repository Zenodo which provides a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13960816>). The name of the dataset follows the convention agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilecosystemservice_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include specific tags of the dataset: "greenhouse gases and climate regulation indicators", "net ecosystem productivity", "Netherlands". The dataset consists in a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset in mind.

The project information will be also indicated in the metadata of the dataset: SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema, and is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version

1.36.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP Soil Serena community (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13960816>). It is Open Access.

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.36.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geopackage file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in carbon fluxes research.

1.36.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The data comes from applying the SERENA GHG cookbook which applied different filters to eliminate NEP values inconsistencies. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.36.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.36.4 Data security

Data security is provided by Zenodo.

1.36.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research and is spatially aggregated.

1.37 SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil sealing of the Netherlands

1.37.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil Sealing cookbook. For the Netherlands, the application was carried out at national scale.

The map of soil sealing (soil threat) was based on classification of multitemporal satellite images and photointerpretation. The methodology uses vegetation and backscatter indices calculated over time series of images, and decision rules. The semi-automatic classification supports the subsequent photointerpretation phase based on national orthophotos and other free VHR satellite images (e.g. through Google Earth or Bing services). The final maps are the product of a binary classification (sealed/not-sealed) having 10 m spatial resolution

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. The selected indicator was degree of soil sealing. By evaluating this degree at two moments in time, the change in soil sealing can be determined.

To create the soil sealing map, we used Sentinel-1 C-band synthetic aperture radar imaging and Sentinel-2 Multispectral Instrument (MSI) (<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>) for the semi-automatic classification, and Google Earth images for the photointerpretation.

Delivered map was prepared in the GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 10 m. File is 6828 MB.

1.37.2 FAIR data

1.37.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (GeoTIFF file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_NL_SOILSEALING_SEALINGDEGREE.TIF") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13960887>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "soil sealing", "remote sensing", "satellite images", "photointerpretation", "The Netherlands". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema in .docx format, and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.37.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP Soil community (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13960887>). It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section). It will be Open Access.

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (GeoTIFF) that can be opened in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.37.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a GeoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil sealing research.

1.37.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA Soil Sealing cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for the Netherlands.

1.37.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.37.4 Data security

Data security is provided by Zenodo.

1.37.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.38 SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil loss by water erosion of Poland

1.38.1 Data summary

The present data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil erosion and soil erosion control cookbook. For Poland we selected 60% of the Polish area, including agricultural land (arable land, grassland, permanent crops). In the IUNG-PIB we store and manage the data only for agricultural land, hence preparing map for other land uses, would be less accurate due to the lack of data for example for soil texture and SOC content.

The map of soil loss by water erosion (soil threat) was based on the RUSLE model.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil loss was used as an indicator for soil erosion (ST).

To create the soil loss map we used data on monthly precipitation from WorldClim for 2018 (R-factor), Corine Land Cover raster data for 2018 (C-factor), SOC content, sand, silt, clay content (previously modelled in IUNG-PIB using DSM approach and QRF algorithm) (K-factor), LS-factor already available to download, as suggested in the cookbook (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/ls-factor-slope-length-and-steepness-factor-eu>), and P-factor also downloaded from the different resource (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/support-practices-factor-p-factor-eu>).

Both delivered maps were prepared in the GeoTIFF format in the resolution of 100m.

Delivered data will be validated by stakeholders from Poland (scientists) in October, 2024.

1.38.2 FAIR data

1.38.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (single band raster file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_PL_EROSION_SOILLOSS.tif") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo, and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017261>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilecosystemservice_indicator). The keywords used to make

the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: “SERENA” “EJP-SOIL”, “erosion”, “water erosion”, “RUSLE”, “Poland”. The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema in .docx format, and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.38.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017261>). It complies with the Zenodo’s platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (Geotiff) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.38.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a single band raster file with associated metadata in .docx format. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil erosion by water modelling.

1.38.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA Erosion and Erosion Control cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Poland. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.38.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in Zenodo the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.38.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (Zenodo).

1.38.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.39 SERENA T3.4 - Map of Soil mass not eroded of Poland

1.39.1 Data summary

The present data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil erosion and soil erosion control cookbook. For Poland we selected 60% of the Polish area, including agricultural land (arable land, grassland, permanent crops). In the IUNG-PIB we store and manage the data only for agricultural land, hence preparing map for other land uses, would be less accurate due to the lack of data for example for soil texture and SOC content.

The map of soil mass not eroded (soil-based ecosystem service (SES)) was based on the RUSLE model.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil mass not eroded was used as an indicator for soil erosion control (SES).

To create the map we used data on monthly precipitation from WorldClim for 2018 (R-factor), Corine Land Cover raster data for 2018 (C-factor), SOC content, sand, silt, clay content (previously modelled in IUNG-PIB using DSM approach and QRF algorithm) (K-factor), LS-factor already available to download, as suggested in the cookbook (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/ls-factor-slope-length-and-steepness-factor-eu>), and P-factor also downloaded from the different resource (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/support-practices-factor-p-factor-eu>).

Both delivered maps were prepared in the GeoTIFF format in the resolution of 100m.

Delivered data will be validated by stakeholders from Poland (scientists) in October, 2024.

1.39.2 FAIR data

1.39.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (single band raster file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_PL_EROSIONCONTROL_SOILMASSNOTERODED.tif") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo, and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14018111>). The name of the data follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilecosystemservice_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the

dataset: “SERENA” “EJP-SOIL”, “erosion control”, “water erosion”, “RUSLE”, “Poland”. The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema in .docx format, and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.39.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14018111>). It complies with the Zenodo’s platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (GeoTIFF) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.39.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a raster file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil erosion control modelling.

1.39.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA Erosion and Erosion Control cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Poland. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.39.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in ZENODO the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.39.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (ZENODO).

1.39.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.40 SERENA T3.2 - Map of soil organic carbon of Portugal

1.40.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA SOC Loss Cookbook (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13993621>). For Portugal, the application was carried out at national scale.

The dataset was mainly produced to test the methodology of the SERENA SOC loss cookbook, and it served as a proof of concept for the cookbook.

The map of soil organic carbon (as an indicator of SOC loss threats) was based on ordinary kriging. The map shows SOC concentration (g kg^{-1}) at national scale.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil organic carbon concentration was used as an indicator for soil organic carbon loss (ST).

To create the soil organic carbon map, we used soil organic carbon (0-0.20 m) data from LUCAS 2018 TOPSOIL data - ESDAC - European Commission (europa.eu) database, which are freely available (LUCAS 2018 TOPSOIL data - ESDAC - European Commission (europa.eu))

Delivered map was prepared in the GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 50 m.

Delivered data was validated by science stakeholders from Portugal (considered experts) in September 2024.

1.40.2 FAIR data

1.40.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geoTIFF file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_PT_SOCLOSS_SOC.tif") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006537>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "SOCLOSS", "SOC", "Geostatistics", "PORTUGAL". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (https://zenodo.org/communities/ejp_soil_research/SERENA)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.40.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP-Soil SERENA community (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006537>). It complies with the Zenodo's platform and follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geoTIFF) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data are open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload, yet a 6-months period of embargo will apply in view of potential publications.

1.40.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil organic carbon modelling.

1.40.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA SOC loss cookbook applying the most updated and freely available for Portugal at national scale. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.40.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated with making the dataset FAIR, as well as for long-term preservation, are unknown, and the dataset creator does not know how to estimate them. SERENA has a data project manager, but once the data is in ZENODO, it is not expected to be curated in the long-term.

1.40.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (ZENODO).

1.40.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.41 SERENA T3.2 - Erosion Control map of Slovakia

1.41.1 Data summary

The present data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil erosion and soil erosion control cookbook for the territory of Slovakia. The map of soil loss by water erosion (soil threat) was based on the RUSLE model or the soil erosion control, the difference between the erosion map without vegetation (C-factor = 1) and the erosion map with vegetation was calculated.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil loss was used as an indicator for soil erosion (ST).

To create the erosion control map, we used these data:

- **R factor** - we used data from 100 automatic rain stations on minute rainfall for about 10-year period (national dataset)
- **K factor** – we used the source proposed in the cookbook from ESDAC dataset: Soil Erodibility (K- Factor) High Resolution dataset for Europe
- **LS factor** – we used the source proposed in the cookbook from ESDAC dataset: LS-factor (Slope Length and Steepness factor) for Slovakia
- **C factor** – we used LPIS database-this has information about crops on agricultural soil. We have values of C factor for all crops.
- **P factor** – we used the source proposed in the cookbook from ESDAC dataset: P factor for Slovakia. This map has values about 0.99 for Slovakia, so P-factor does not have much effect on the resulting erosion.

The delivered map was prepared in GeoTIFF format in the resolution of 500 * 500 m.

1.41.2 FAIR data

1.41.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_SK_EROSION_ErosionControl.tif") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13993746>). The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "Grant n 862695", "soil erosion control", "soil-based ecosystem service", "RUSLE", "Slovakia". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema will be created and includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language

- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.41.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13993746>). It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geoTIFF) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS Pro).

1.41.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil erosion by water modelling.

1.41.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA Erosion and Erosion Control cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Slovakia. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.41.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in ZENODO the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.41.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (ZENODO).

1.41.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.42 SERENA T3.2 - Map of Soil loss by water erosion of Slovakia

1.42.1 Data summary

The present data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil erosion and soil erosion control cookbook for the territory of Slovakia. The map of soil loss by water erosion (soil threat) was based on the RUSLE model.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil loss was used as an indicator for soil erosion (ST).

To create the soil loss map we used these data:

- **R factor** - we used data from 100 automatic rain stations on minute rainfall for about 10-year period (national dataset)
- **K factor** – we used the source proposed in the cookbook from ESDAC dataset: Soil Erodibility (K- Factor) High Resolution dataset for Europe
- **LS factor** – we used the source proposed in the cookbook from ESDAC dataset: LS-factor (Slope Length and Steepness factor) for Slovakia
- **C factor** – we used LPIS database-this has information about crops on agricultural soil. We have values of C factor for all crops.
- **P factor** – we used the source proposed in the cookbook from ESDAC dataset: P factor for Slovakia. This map has values about 0.99 for Slovakia, so P-factor does not have much effect on the resulting erosion.

The delivered map was prepared in GeoTIFF format in the resolution of 500 * 500 m.

1.42.2 FAIR data

1.42.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (file:"SERENA_EJPSOIL_SK_EROSION_soilerosion.tif") is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13993556>. The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "Grant n 862695", "soil erosion", "RUSLE", "Slovakia", "erosion cookbook". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema will be created and includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords

- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.42.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13993556>). It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geoTIFF) that can be open in a number of GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS Pro).

1.42.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a single band raster file with associated metadata in .docx format. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil erosion by water modelling.

1.42.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA Erosion and Erosion Control cookbook applying the most updated and accurate datasets available for Slovakia. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.42.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in ZENODO the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.42.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (ZENODO).

1.42.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.43 SERENA T3.2 - Evaluation of soil threats and ecosystem service evolution under climate, land use or management changes. Deliverable report 3.4 and literature review.

1.43.1 Data summary

Based on an intensive literature review (doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969537) and results from previous experiences in member states a scenario framework was developed (climate, land use, and management changes) and common methodologies (statistical methods, simple and/or more sophisticated models) were identified, used or validated to forecast how selected soil ecosystem services (SES) and soil threats (ST) will change according to climate, land-use and management changes. In contrast to WP5 we focus in WP3/Task 3, Deliverable 3.4. on forecasts of changes of various soil indicators on site, regional or national scale, and could rely on soil maps with high resolution that are maintained by several member states. Due to the lack of available methods/models, missing experience by member states or the availability of input data no forecasts could be done for the SES environmental pollution control, habitat for biodiversity, pest and disease control, soil contamination, loss of diversity and salinization. 6 member states (Austria, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Ireland and Poland) were able to run scenario analysis with different methods.

1.43.2 FAIR data

1.43.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (document, excel tables and maps) is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13945383> for the deliverable 3.4 and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969536> for the literature review for milestone 3.4). The name of the datasets follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (National SoilHUBS: Assessment of (bundles of) Soil functions/threats/ecosystem services at different scales). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in the SERENA community. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "scenario analysis", "climate change", "management" or land use change. The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

1.43.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13945383> for the deliverable 3.4 and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969536> for the literature review for milestone 3.4). It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset are results of the scenario analysis in form of the deliverable report, excel tables and maps and the table with all used papers used for the literature review.

1.43.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as document, excel files and as maps. The format is interoperable across software and platforms.

1.43.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC-BY). The maps that were produced for the deliverable report D3.4 is coming from the 6 member states (Austria, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Latvia, Poland) and will be uploaded to ZENODO by each responsible person using the link to the deliverable report Doi.

1.43.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in ZENODO the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.43.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (ZENODO).

1.43.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.44 SERENA T4.2 - Extending LUCAS with Corine Land Cover

1.44.1 Data summary

In order to assess Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) response to Land Use Change (LUC), T4.2 of SERENA leverages topsoil samples from LUCAS-soil, a 10% subset of the LUCAS survey. To recover LUC, it uses data from five sequential waves of the LUCAS survey in 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, and 2018, but soil samples were taken only in 2009 (2012 in Bulgaria and Romania), 2015, and 2018. Based on models, the literature tends to consider that it takes decades for soil carbon sequestration to reach equilibrium, but there is little evidence to quantify how long it actually takes. To augment the temporal and spatial scope of our carbon response analysis, we adopt a machine learning model to predict ground-truthed land-use changes - as observed in LUCAS - with Corine Land Cover (CLC) data based on aerial photographs. The trained model is then used to predict land use based at LUCAS-soil points since 1990, and detect probable land-use changes having occurred between 1990 and 2006.

The model is utilized to estimate the probability of land use being cropland, grassland, or forest for the years 1990, 2000, 2006, 2012, and 2018, in cases where land use information is missing for LUCAS survey points. Specifically, we assign the land cover category with the highest probability to each point. If the highest probability among cropland, grassland, or forest does not exceed 50%, we label the

points as “Other”. Moreover, we use the machine learning model to assess the uncertainty of these LUC predictions. In a bootstrap-like sensitivity analysis, we draw 100 times a land use on each LUCAS point according to the probabilities given by the machine learning model.

We use this novel dataset to produce upscaled estimates of SOC response over time to LUCS with high precision across EU. We then use the estimates to publish country specific emission factors, compliant with the IPCC guidelines and the LULUCF Regulation, and ready for use in national GHG inventories. These data could be useful for analysing the effects of LUC on Lucas Soil before it is implemented.

1.44.2 FAIR data

1.44.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

These data are actually used to perform a statistical analysis, they will be put on the dataverse <https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataverse/inrae> once the paper is published.

The provision of metadata will comply with the platform which uses metadata standards (DataCite), required keywords with link to standard vocabularies, enables versioning. The platform uses the DOI as persistent identifier.

1.44.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

These data will have the same copyright and licence than initial CLC and LUCAS Soil data. They will be downloadable in the Serena dataverse in a csv format. A Readme file will be also available in the Serena dataverse describing the different files using the template proposed by the data repository. The data could be accessed using any spreadsheet software.

1.44.2.3 Making data interoperable:

We will use a JSON metadata file using as much as possible standard vocabularies or ontologies for describing the data of the csv files.

1.44.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

The data will follow the rules from JRC regarding the LUCAS Soil data for re-usability. An authorization will be asked to the JRC to know if these data can be made openly accessible.

If data can be made openly accessible, they will be available for re-use at the end of the project with embargo until the paper is published.

The Serena dataverse is part of the French research repository and thus will follow the rules of this repository which guaranties an access to the files for a minimum of 5 years, renewable after publication of the dataset.

1.44.3 Allocation of resources

Making these data available is part of the cost of the Serena project for the data producer team.

The administration of the Serena dataverse is taken in charge by INRAE.

1.44.4 Data security

Data security is provided by the dataverse.

1.44.5 Ethical aspects

As the data are compiled from the LUCAS Soil data without aggregation, they are faced with personal data issues linked to the coordinates of the sampling sites.

1.45 SERENA T3.3 – Maps for Soil loss by water from climate change scenarios for Austria

1.45.1 Data summary

The present data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA Soil erosion and soil erosion control cookbook (Buttafuoco *et al.*, 2024). The maps of soil loss by water erosion (soil threat) were based on the RUSLE model.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. Soil loss was used as an indicator for the soil threat soil erosion.

The methods and data used to create the soil loss map are described in Buttafuoco *et al.* (2024) and Hessel *et al.* (2024).

The maps of relative soil loss are provided as .tiff files with a resolution of 25 m.

This dataset contains the change of modelled annual soil loss rates for changing R-factor according to RCP4.5 and RPC8.5 climate scenarios, relative to modelled soil loss in the base scenario, using R-factor calculated for the 1990-2021 period for the country of Austria. For each climate scenario, four periods were considered: 1991-2020, 2021-2040, 2041-2060 and 2061-2080. The RUSLE-based soil loss calculations were done according to the SERENA/EJP-Soil soil erosion control cookbook and are described in the respective project deliverables D3.3 and D3.4.

1.45.2 FAIR data

1.45.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset was published open access under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13991805> via the Zenodo repository. The published zip-folder contains the raw data as .tiff files with auxiliary files.

As the dataset is described by SERENA/EJP-Soil Deliverable D3.4, the DOI of this Deliverable was linked for better findability: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13945384>.

Keywords for search in zenodo.org and in the metadata file: SERENA project, EJPSOIL, Grant no 862695, D3.4

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema in .txt format, and is part of the dataset. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact

- Links
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.45.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

All data are provided in the open access repository as it was put into the survey. There are .tiff files which are packed in a .zip-file, hence accessible with standard GIS software.

1.45.2.3 Making data interoperable:

See explanations above – the raster data can be included into any GIS workflow and easily operable without any special requirements. The terms follow common usage in soil erosion by water modelling.

1.45.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

Data is open for re-use und CC BY 4.0 as long as the repository zenodo.org exists.

1.45.3 Allocation of resources

Making the dataset accessible costed around 4 hours of working time, funded by the grant mentioned in the dataset keywords.

1.45.4 Data security

For data security, the highly secure repository zenodo.org is used. There is a copy stored and available at the internal server system of the main authors. No sensitive data is included.

1.45.5 Ethical aspects

No ethical or legal issues impacting the data sharing.

References

Buttafuoco *et al.*, 2024. Cookbook to evaluate indicators of soil threats, soil-based ES and their associated bundles over scenarios of change. SERENA deliverable 2.3.2 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13993620>

Hessel R, G Buttafuoco, E Medina-Roldán, D Smiraglia, J Coblinski, L Kuk, B Lemercier, S Pindral, J Reyes Rojas, R Lorenzetti, C Pesch, K Amalevičiūtė-Volungė, S Asins, F Assennato, A Astover, Z Bakacsi, A Benő, G Bondi, T Brunner, S Callewaert, K Cockx, J Cruijssen, P Csontos, E Doñate, A Fahy, V Feiza, C B Foldal, A Gaillot, L Gardin, C Gedeon, D Josipovic, P Kassai, T Kikas, M Kocsis, A Laborczi, D Luts, J Makovníková, D Montagne, K Oorts, L O’Sullivan, B Pálka, L Pásztor, E Putku, N Riitano, N Saby, E Schmaltz, V Shahrokh, B Szabó, G Szatmári, M Trip, F Ungaro, J Volungevičius, T Weninger, R Žydelis. 2024. Assessment of Soil Threats and Ecosystem Services from each MS with the harmonized procedures. SERENA deliverable 3.3, 224 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13991087>

1.46 Map of soil organic carbon for France

1.46.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the methodology of SERENA SOC loss cookbook.

Random forest was used for the prediction of the SOC concentration using the general DSM workflow implemented in the R package *Seedling* (Genova, G., Poggio, L., Kempen, B., & Colman, B. (2024). DSM Workflow Seedling. ISRIC - World Soil Information. <https://doi.org/10.17027/ISRIC-FSX2-2691>.)

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats (ST). Soil organic carbon concentration was used as an indicator for soil organic carbon loss (ST).

To compile the soil organic carbon map, we used soil organic carbon (0-30 cm) data of the French Soil Information and Monitoring System (SIMS), which are not publicly available. The data are described in the following paper: Mulder, V.L., Martin, M., Lacoste, M., Saby, N., Richer-De-Forges, A., Arrouays, D., 2014. Controlling factors explaining soil carbon in relation to soil depth for French soils, in: ELS 2014, The Earth Living Skin: Soil, Life and Climate Change.

The selection of environmental covariates, which are then used to model and map SOC content, was based on the 'scorpan' model: (s) soil properties, (c) climate, (o) organisms, (r) relief, (p) parent material, (a) age and (n) spatial coordinates. These covariates are described in the following paper: Dobarco, M.R., Bourennane, H., Arrouays, D., Saby, N.P., Cousin, I., Martin, M.P., 2019. Uncertainty assessment of GlobalSoilMap soil available water capacity products: A French case study. *Geoderma*, 344, 14–30.

Delivered map was prepared in GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 100 x 100 m.

1.46.2 FAIR data

1.46.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (geoTIFF file: "SERENA_EJPSOIL_FR_SOCLOSS_SOC.tif") will be available in the SERENA dataverse https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataverse/ejp_soil_serena.

The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilthreat_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "SOCLOSS", "SOC", "DSM", "France". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

A metadata schema has been created and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact

- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.46.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset will be uploaded in the Serena dataverse and will be provided a DOI.

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geoTIFF) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

1.46.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in soil organic carbon modelling.

1.46.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

The dataset licence will be the etalab 2.0 which is compatible with a CC-BY licence.

1.46.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in the dataverse the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.46.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (<https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/>).

1.46.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.47 Literature review Task 3.3

1.47.1 Data summary

We reviewed existing modelling studies from all over the world focusing on scenario analyses of SES and ST including climate change, land use change and management scenarios. A publication has been submitted to “Science of the total environment” and is currently being reviewed. The title of the manuscript is: Assessing and mapping soil ecosystem services and soil threats changes in agroecosystems through scenario-based approaches – a systematic review.

Work was split between various authors. All Co-authors that are mentioned in the first page were working on either one or more SES or one ST. Excel sheets were prepared by INRAE and BFW to ensure the comparability of results that members extracted from the papers found. Literature search was done in Scopus and Web of Science. The aim of the literature review was mainly to:

- understand how different drivers of global change are most commonly studied in scientific literature.
- identify which SES and ST are most commonly studied and how they are assessed and mapped in scenario-based approaches.
- Finally, provide a preliminary discussion on how soil properties are represented in these scenario-based approaches.

After screening the Web and sorting out unusable papers, we found 230 published articles related to 7 SES and 10 ST.

1.47.2 FAIR data

1.47.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (Excel table with all used papers and a Zotero list with all papers that were used for the literature review and for the above-mentioned publication) will be available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it will be provided with a DOI identifier. The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (National SoilHUBS: Assessment of (bundles of) Soil functions/threats/ecosystem services at different scales). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in the SERENA community. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: "SERENA" "EJP-SOIL", "review", "global", "literature". The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset.

1.47.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset will be uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. It complies with the Zenodo's platform and it will follow the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset is an excel table and a Zotero file.

The paper will be uploaded as soon as it is accepted for publication.

1.47.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as an Excel file and as a Zotero literature list. The format is interoperable across software and platforms.

1.47.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

The dataset licence will be the Creative Commons Attribution license (CC-BY). The extracted data comes from the papers that were used for the literature review. Data were later on harmonized to make it comparable and to be sure that the same wording is used in each column.

1.47.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in ZENODO the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.47.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (ZENODO).

1.47.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.48 Soil based ecosystem services individual assessments and bundles results

1.48.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the methodology describe in detail in the deliverable D5.2 (Coblinski *et al.*, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13950477>)

The dataset contains the evaluation of 4 soil ecosystem services and associated bundles for current period and in 2050 for two climate change scenarios corresponding to two contrasted Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5).

These maps were produced using GIS software and digital soil mapping approaches to map selected indicators of the different soil threats.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats.

Delivered map was prepared in the GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 1000 m.

	geodataset name	Description
Individual assessment of soil ecosystem services expressed in original scale Evaluation of the 5 SES for 3 scenarios (current, 2050_ssp126 or 2050_ssp585) The SES are expressed in original scale	ErosCont_2050_SSP126.tif ErosCont_2050_SSP585.tif ErosCont_current.tif	ErosCont means Erosion control, Amount of soil not eroded by water ($t\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$)
	FloodCont_current.tif FloodCont_2050_SSP126.tif FloodCont_2050_SSP585.tif	FloodCont means Flood control, Soil water retention capacity (mm)
	WatProd_2050_SSP126.tif WatProd_2050_SSP585.tif WatProd_current.tif	WaterProd means Water production, Water yield ($mm\ yr^{-1}$)
	PrimProd_2050_SSP126.tif PrimProd_2050_SSP585.tif PrimProd_current.tif	PrimProd means Primary biomass production, Net primary production ($gC\ m^{-2}\ yr^{-1}$)
	ClimReg_current.tif ClimReg_2050_SSP126.tif ClimReg_2050_SSP585.tif	ClimReg, Climate regulation, Net ecosystem productivity ($gC\ m^{-2}\ yr^{-1}$)
Individual assessment of soil ecosystem services expressed in classes	ErosCont_2050_SSP126_classes.tif ErosCont_2050_SSP585_classes.tif ErosCont_current_classes.tif FloodCont_2050_SSP126_classes.tif FloodCont_2050_SSP585_classes.tif FloodCont_current_classes.tif WatProd_2050_SSP126_classes.tif WatProd_2050_SSP585_classes.tif WatProd_current_classes.tif PrimProd_2050_SSP126_classes.tif PrimProd_2050_SSP585_classes.tif	We have considered the SES values corresponding to the 40% and 60% quantiles of the current situation to define the thresholds for low and high intensity levels of SES, respectively. These threshold values were then used for the two 2050 scenarios

	PrimProd_current_classes.tif ClimReg_2050_SSP126_classes.tif ClimReg_2050_SSP585_classes.tif ClimReg_current_classes.tif	
Bundles of soil ecosystem services	SES_bundles_current_raw.tif SES_bundles_SSP126.tif SES_bundles_SSP585.tif	Id of the SES bundles for the 3 scenarios We obtained 21 bundles

To compute the above raster, we used the following data available online

Parameters	Variables	Unit	Raw resolution	Source	SES	
Climate	Monthly precipitation	mm	1 km	worldclim.org/	WatProd; ErosCont	
	Annual precipitation	mm yr ⁻¹				
	Minimum temperature	°C	1 km	worldclim.org/	WatProd	
	Maximum temperature	°C				
	Annual mean temperature	°C				
	Mean diurnal range	°C				
	Isothermality	No unit				
	Temperature seasonality	°C				
	Max temp of warm month	°C				
	Temp annual range	°C	1 km	worldclim.org/	FloodCont	
	Mean temp of wet quarter	°C				
	Mean temp of driest quarter	°C				
	Precipitation of driest month	mm				
	Precipitation seasonality	Fraction				
	Precip of warmest quarter	mm				
	Precip of coldest quarter	mm				
	Soil	Clay	g 100g ⁻¹	250 m		
		Sand	g 100g ⁻¹	250 m		
Silt		g 100g ⁻¹	250 m	https://data.isric.org/geonetwork/srv/en/catalog.search#	FloodCont; ErosCont	
Coarse fragments		g 100g ⁻¹	250 m			
SOC content		g kg ⁻¹	250 m			
Soil depth		m	1 km	esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/europea-n-soil-database-v2-		

				raster-library-1kmx1km	
Topography	Aspect	No unit	25 m	land.copernicus.eu/imagery-in-situ/eu-dem/eu-dem-v1.1/view	FloodCont; ErosCont
	Elevation	m	25 m		
	Slope	%	25 m ²		
Land use	Land use classes	No unit	100 m	joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/luisa_en	FloodCont; ErosCont
Support Practices	Contour farming	No unit	100 m	esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/themes/support-practices-factor	ErosCont
	Stone walls	No unit	100 m		
	Grass margins	No unit	100 m		
Vegetation	NPP	gC m ² yr ⁻¹	55 km	https://data.isimip.org/search/simulation_round/ISIMIP3b/	BiomProd; ClimReg
	RH	gC m ² yr ⁻¹	55 km		

1.48.2 FAIR data

1.48.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The spatial datasets will be available in the general science repository of entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr in the Serena dataverse (https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataverse/ejp_soil_serena) with a DOI identifier.

A metadata schema has been created and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.48.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset contains several rasters.

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geoTIFF) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS, R terra package) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data are open accessible in the ERDG repository after upload, yet a 6-months period of embargo will be applied in view of potential publications.

1.48.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms.

1.48.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

The dataset licence will be the etalab 2.0 which is compatible with a CC-BY licence.

1.48.2.5 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.48.3 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr).

1.48.4 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.49 Soil threats individual assessments and bundles results for 2050 in Europe

1.49.1 Data summary

The data was prepared according to the methodology describe in details in the deliverable D5.1 (Coblinski *et al.*, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13891492>)

The dataset contains the evaluation of 5 soil threats in 2050 and associated bundles for two climate change scenarios corresponding to two contrasted Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5).

These maps were produced using GIS software and digital soil mapping approaches to map selected indicators of the different soil threats.

The objective of SERENA project was to develop methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats.

Delivered map was prepared in the GeoTIFF raster format at the resolution of 1000 m.

Table 1. List of the raster files and description provided in the dataset.

geodataset name	Description
Individual assessment of soil parameters: BulkDensity_2050_SSP126.tif BulkDensity_2050_SSP585.tif BulkDensity_current.tif SOCstock_2050_SSP126.tif SOCstock_2050_SSP585.tif SOCstock_current.tif Erosion_2050_SSP126.tif	Maps of individual assessment of soil threat indicator for current scenario and 2 future scenarios (2050 SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5). Bulk density evaluation of 0-30 cm (BulkDensity) Soil Carbon stock up to 1m (SOCstock)

Erosion_2050_SSP585.tif Sealing_2050.tif	Sheet and rill erosion by water assessed by the revised universal soil loss equation (Erosion) Degree of soil sealing (Sealing)
Evaluation of soil threats, classified: Compaction_2050_SSP126_classes.tif Compaction_2050_SSP585_classes.tif Erosion_2050_SSP126_classes.tif Erosion_2050_SSP585_classes.tif Sealing_2050_class.tif SOCloss_2050_SSP126_classes.tif SOCloss_2050_SSP585_classes.tif	Compaction: changes in bulk density in topsoil (0-30 cm), expressed in classes of relative change (<-40%, -40% -10%, -10% – 10%, > 10%) SOC loss (up to 1 m deep) expressed in classes of relative change (-40% -10%, -10% – 10%, > 10%) Erosion: sheet and rill erosion by water by 2050 using RUSLE equation: soil loss intensity classes 0-1 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ : negligible soil loss; 1-2 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ : very slight soil loss; 2-5 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ : slight soil loss; 5-10 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ : moderate soil loss; > 10 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ : severe soil loss. Changes in soil sealing by 2050: Soil sealing by 2050: classes of soil sealing change between 2012 and 2050 (-80%-30%, 30% 100%)
Bundles of soil threats ST_bundles_2050_SSP126.tif ST_bundles_2050_SSP585.tif	Soil Threats bundles map by 2050 under land use and under SSP5-8.5 and SSP1-2.6

Since several ST indicators need soil parameters (change in SOC or bulk density and erosion), climate data (same indicators) or land use (change in SOC or bulk density and soil artificialization), the use of different data bases as input data could induce discrepancies that might arise from the inherent variations in the different sources. To avoid this drawback, we chose a unique soil database per data type, that is SoilGrids for soil data, WorldClim for climate, and LUISA for land use. Data sources used to assess SOC stock change, soil bulk density change and erosion by 2050 are synthetized in Table 2 to 4.

Table 2. Environmental-based covariates used in the predictive model using DSM approach for the assessment of soil compaction and SOC loss.

SCORPAN variables	Covariates	Unit	Spatial raw resolution	Source
Soil	Bulk density	kg/dm ³	250 m	SoilGrids data.isric.org/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/home
	Clay	%	250 m	
	Sand	%	250 m	
	Silt	%	250 m	
	Cation exchange capacity	cmol(c)/kg	250 m	
	Coarse fragments	%	250 m	
	Organic carbon density	kg/m ³	250 m	
	pH	pH	250 m	
	Soil depth	m	1 km	
Soil water content 33 kPa	kPa	250 m	OpenGeoHub zenodo.org/record/2784001#.YxCkbXZByCh	
Topography	Aspect	no unit	25 m	Copernicus land.copernicus.eu/imagery-in-situ/eu-dem/eu-dem-v1.1/view
	Elevation	m	25 m	
	Slope	%	25 m	
Climate	Bioclimatic variables*	-	1 km	See table 4
Land use	Land use classes	no unit		See table 4

Table 3. Input data for the assessment of the individual RUSLE factors

RUSLE factors	Input data	Unit	Spatial raw resolution		Source
P factor Support practices	P factor	-	100 m	ESDAC	esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/themes/support-practices-factor
LS factor Slop length and steepness	LS factor	-	100 m	ESDAC	esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/ls-factor-slope-length-and-steepness-factor-eu
C factor Cover management	Land use	No unit	100 m	LUISA	joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/luisa_en
R factor Rainfall erosivity	Annual precipitation	mm	1 km	WorldClim	www.worldclim.org/
	Monthly precipitation	mm	1 km		
K factor Soil erodibility	Clay	%	250 m	SoilGrids	data.isric.org/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/home
	Sand	%	250 m		
	Silt	%	250 m		
	Soil organic carbon content	g/kg	250 m		

Table 4. List of variables used to represent climate and land use changes scenarios used to assess soil compaction, SOC loss and soil erosion, and the respective source. Climate data used for 2050 were the mean of the results produced by the two ACCESS-CM2 and HadGEM3-GC31-LL global climate models for the two selected SSPs

Parameters	Variables	Unit	Raw resolution	Database	Period
Precipitation	Monthly total precipitation	mm			
Bioclimatic variables	Annual mean temperature	°C			
	Mean Diurnal Range	°C			
	Isothermality	No unit			
	Temperature Seasonality	°C			
	Max Temperature of Warmest Month	°C			
	Min Temperature of Coldest Month	°C			
	Temperature Annual Range	°C			
	Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter	°C			
	Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter	°C	1 km	<i>worldclim.org</i> (Dix <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Good, 2019)	Historical (1970-2000) to 2050 (SSP 1.2-6 and SSP 5.8-5)
	Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter	°C			
	Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter	°C			
	Annual Precipitation	mm			
	Precipitation of Wettest Month	mm			
	Precipitation of Driest Month	mm			
	Precipitation Seasonality	Fraction			
Precipitation of Wettest Quarter	mm				
Precipitation of Driest Quarter	mm				
Precipitation of Warmest Quarter	mm				
Precipitation of Coldest Quarter	mm				
Land use	Land use classes	No unit	100 m	<i>LUISA - joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/luisa_en</i> (Joint Research Centre, 2017)	2012 to 2050

1.49.2 FAIR data

1.49.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The spatial datasets will be available in the general science repository of entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr in the Serena dataverse (https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataverse/ejp_soil_serena) with a DOI identifier.

A metadata schema has been created and it is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- History/version
- Authors and contact

1.49.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset contains several rasters.

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geoTIFF) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open-source (e.g., QGIS, R terra package) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data are open accessible in the ERDG repository after upload, yet a 6-months period of embargo will be applied in view of potential publications.

1.49.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geoTIFF file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms.

1.49.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

The dataset licence will be the etalab 2.0 which is compatible with a CC-BY licence.

1.49.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.49.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr).

1.49.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.49.6 Reference

Dix, M., Bi, D., Dobrohotoff, P., Fiedler, R., Harman, I., Law, R., Mackallah, C., Marsland, S., O'Farrell, S., Rashid, H., Srbinovsky, J., Sullivan, A., Trenham, C., Vohralik, P., Watterson, I., Williams, G., Woodhouse, M., Bodman, R., Dias, F.B., Domingues, C.M., Hannah, N., Heerdegen, A., Savita, A., Wales, S., Allen, C., Druken, K., Evans, B., Richards, C., Ridzwan, S.M., Roberts, D., Smillie, J., Snow, K., Ward, M., Yang, R., 2019. CSIRO-ARCCSS ACCESS-CM2 model output prepared for CMIP6 CMIP. <https://doi.org/10.22033/ESGF/CMIP6.2281>

Good, P., 2019. MOHC HadGEM3-GC31-LL model output prepared for CMIP6 ScenarioMIP. <https://doi.org/10.22033/ESGF/CMIP6.10845>

Joint Research Centre, 2017. The LUISA territorial reference scenario 2017: a technical description. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.

1.50 Net Ecosystem Productivity Cookbook

1.50.1 Data summary

The present dataset corresponds to a derived dataset (SERENA NEP dataset hereafter) to analyse the relationship between Net Ecosystem Productivity (NEP) components and a number of spatially-exhaustive environmental variables in wheat croplands/rotations, with a focus on the EU. The SERENA NEP dataset is derived from eddy-covariance data for those stations in the Fluxnet network with data for wheat, and:

- MODIS MOD17A2HGF Collection
- Daily soil moisture data (derived from Zhang et al. 2023)
- World Climate maximum monthly temperature
- World Climate minimum monthly temperature

SERENA had, among others, the objective of developing methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats. NEP was used as an indicator of greenhouse gases and climate regulation supported by soils.

For this purpose, the relationship between Fluxnet NEP (the negative of net ecosystem exchange), its components; and those variables above was investigated through a number of statistical approaches. The dataset was compiled using a data collection and management approach implemented in R.

The SERENA NEP dataset in comma separated values format has a size of 551.6 Kb.

The data is useful as a research tool to investigate CO₂ fluxes in the region for the SERENA consortium and other researchers.

1.50.2 FAIR data

1.50.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The dataset (csv file: “SERENA_EJPSOIL_GHG_NEP_cookbook.csv”) is available in the general science repository of Zenodo; and it is provided with a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14002496>). The name of the dataset follows the fact that it was created in a part of the project aimed at developing “cookbooks”. The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include a minimum number of identifier words relating the dataset to the SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number and specific tags of the dataset: “greenhouse gases and climate regulation indicators”, “net ecosystem productivity”, “ecosystem respiration”, “gross primary productivity”, “GPP MODIS”, “monthly temperature”, “soil moisture”. The dataset consists of a single version since there are no upgradable versions to the dataset in mind.

A metadata schema file (SERENA_EJPSOIL_GHG_NEP_cookbook_metadata.txt) has been created explaining the structure of the file and it provides details on the variables present.

1.50.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14002496>). It complies with the Zenodo’s platform and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (.csv) that can be open in a number of applications both open (e.g., LibreOffice Calc) and proprietary (MS Excel).

1.50.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a comma separated values file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in carbon fluxes research.

1.50.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution license (CC-BY). The data comes from applying the SERENA GHG cookbook which applied different filters to eliminate NEP values inconsistencies. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.50.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make it the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in ZENODO the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.50.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (ZENODO).

1.50.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.50.6 References

Zhang, Y., Liang, S., Ma, H., He, T., Wang, Q., Li, B., Xu, J., Zhang, G., Liu, X., Xiong, C., 2023. Generation of global 1-km daily soil moisture product from 2000 to 2020 using ensemble learning. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data Discuss.* 2023, 1–37.

1.51 Deliverable T2.2 soil threats and soil ecosystem services of interest in SERENA

1.51.1 Data summary

In Task 2.2, we discussed definitions of soil threats (ST) and soil-based ecosystem services (SES) to be further analysed in SERENA. In this process, we held information from literature search and the results from the national prioritization of the ST and SES. This dataset is an Excel with sheets of literature study and the national prioritization from participation countries.

1.51.2 FAIR data

1.51.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The final report (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10389896>) and the Excel file (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13940435>) were uploaded in the open-source repository ZENODO. The name of the dataset follows the conventions agreed upon in SERENA. The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA: “SERENA”, “Horizon 2020 grant number 862695”, deliverable number “D2.2” and specific tags of the dataset: “description and definition”, “soil threats and ecosystem services”, “prioritization”.

1.51.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the SERENA/EJP-Soil communities. It complies with the Zenodo’s platform, and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

1.51.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as an Excel file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across software and platforms. The terms follow common usage.

1.51.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution license (CC-BY).

1.51.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in ZENODO the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.51.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (ZENODO).

1.51.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.52 Map of SESs/STs Bundles of Emilia-Romagna, Italy

1.52.1 Data summary

The present dataset corresponds to 2 maps of soil-based ecosystem services for the area of Emilia-Romagna, Italy. The maps are the result of applying the bundles cookbook developed in SERENA/EJP-Soil to the area of interest (AOI) input data ("SERENA_EJPSOIL_IT_bundles.gpkg"); and a variation of the cookbook to the other geodata (SERENA_EJPSOIL_IT_bundles_previous.gpkg). The resulting bundles are clusters of SESs/STs where the intra-cluster variability is lower than the inter-cluster variability in the mean values of the selected SESs/STs to identify the bundles.

SERENA had, among others, the objective of developing methods to calculate and map soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats and their bundles.

For this purpose, the bundles in the present geodatasets were determined from spatially-explicit datasets (more details below)

The 2 geodatasets of bundles are in vector format and are:

Bundles' geodataset name	Description	Size
SERENA_EJPSOIL_IT_bundles.gpkg	Soil-based ecosystem services map, resulting from applying the bundles cookbook developed in SERENA/EJP-Soil to the area of interest (AOI) input data of Emilia-Romagna, Italy. The resulting bundles are clusters of SESs/STs where the intra-cluster variability is lower than the inter-cluster variability in the mean values of the selected SESs/STs to identify the bundles. The bundles in the present geodatasets were determined from 3 spatially-explicit datasets to which the bundles cookbook was applied within the AOI: (1) Emilia-Romagna soil C stock, (2) Emilia-Romagna soil erosion control, and (3) Net ecosystem productivity in early summer for Emilia-Romagna developed in SERENA. The nominal spatial resolution of the dataset is 500m. Because the indicator is rendered spatial in association only with wheat fields (either common or durum), several "gaps" are present. Other big gaps appear as a result of a data gaps in the layers used to calculate NEP.	455.4 Mb

SERENA_EJPSOIL_IT_bundles_previous.gpkg	Bundle map in which the input geodata are 7 soil-based ecosystem services. Details are found in Medina-Roldán et al. 2024 Geoderma, 448, 116962	17.8 Mb
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Although the dataset needs further validation, it is useful as a research tool to investigate co-occurrence of SESs and STs for the SERENA consortium and other researchers.

1.52.2 FAIR data

1.52.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

The geodatasets (geopackage files: see names above) are available in the general science repository Zenodo which provides a DOI identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14001697>). The name of the datasets follows the convention agreed upon in SERENA's WP3 (project_country_soilecosystemservice_indicator). The keywords used to make the dataset findable were agreed upon in SERENA. They include specific tags of the dataset: "soil-based ecosystem services co-occurrence", "Emilia-Romagna". The dataset correspond to single versions since there are no upgradable versions to the datasets in mind.

The project information will be also indicated in the metadata of the dataset: SERENA project, grant number, deliverable number.

A metadata schema has been created following the QGIS schema, and is part of the dataset file properties. The Metadata includes the following info:

- Title
- Object type
- Language
- Abstract/description of the dataset
- Dataset keyword categories
- Dataset keywords
- Licence type
- Geographic info: layer CRS, extent, etc.
- Contact
- Links (at the moment I included a link to the sharepoint, but when the information to add to Zenodo is ready this will be used)
- History/version

1.52.2.2 Making data openly accessible:

The dataset was uploaded to Zenodo in the EJP-Soil Serena community (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14001697>). It complies with the Zenodo's platform, and it follows the information that was agreed upon in the Final Meeting of the project (see previous section).

The dataset uses an open-source, platform-independent format (geopackage) that can be opened in many GIS applications both open (e.g., QGIS) and proprietary (ArcGIS).

The data are open accessible in the Zenodo repository after upload, yet a 6-months period of embargo will apply in view of potential publications.

1.52.2.3 Making data interoperable:

As stated, the dataset is provided as a geopackage file with associated metadata. The format is interoperable across GIS software and platforms. The terms follow common usage in ecosystem services bundles research.

1.52.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

The dataset licence is the Creative Commons Attribution license (CC-BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The data comes from applying the SERENA bundles cookbook. No further QA has been applied to the dataset.

1.52.3 Allocation of resources

The costs associated to make the dataset FAIR as well as for long-term preservation are unknown, and the creator of the dataset does not know how to estimate this. SERENA has a data project manager, but once in ZENODO the data are not expected to be curated at the long-term.

1.52.4 Data security

Data security in terms of storage depends on the repository (ZENODO).

1.52.5 Ethical aspects

The data is not restricted by legal and ethical issues as far as it is generated in the context of biophysical ecological indicators research.

1.52.6 References

Medina-Roldán, E., Lorenzetti, R., Calzolari, C., & Ungaro, F. (2024). Disentangling soil-based ecosystem services synergies, trade-offs, multifunctionality, and bundles: A case study at regional scale (NE Italy) to support environmental planning. *Geoderma*, 448, 116962.

